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Energy
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GEMMA Generation IV Materials Maturity

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Proceedings of the Workshop on Welding technologies for Generation-IV systems, their qualifications and residual stress modelling

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Starting date	Due date	Actual date	Delay*	Nature
	30.11.2021	30.11.2021	--	R
Description of the activities: The JRC has organized an online workshop around the topics addressed in GEMMA Work Package 2 – Welding development and characterization – on 4 and 5 October 2021. This report presents a summary of the Workshop proceedings. The individual presentations can be found in Annex C to this report.				
Author:		WP Leader:	Coordinator:	
Carsten Ohms, Kamil Tuček		Gianclaudio Ferro	Pietro Agostini	

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1. Introduction

This report constitutes Deliverable D6.4 of the Horizon 2020 co-funded collaboration project Generation IV Materials Maturity – GEMMA. It covers the proceedings of a dissemination workshop on the activities of GEMMA Work Package 2 – Welding development and characterization.

Twelve presentations have been solicited by the workshop organizers, addressing the topics of Work Package 2. This included: (i) production of welds in stainless steel grades 316L and 316L(N) in accordance with the provisions of the RCC-MRx code; (ii) characterizations of these welds; (iii) the respective RCC-MRx code requirements; (iv) measurements and predictions of welding residual stresses and their considerations in structural integrity; and (v) identification of remaining knowledge gaps.

Predominantly members of the GEMMA consortium and members of the NeT European Network (European Network on Neutron Techniques Standardization for Structural Integrity), which pursues objectives similar to GEMMA in the welding residual stress domain, have been invited to participate. With more than 35 scientists and engineers from 11 countries following the invitation, the Workshop has received a very good level of interest in the targeted community.

A summary of the Workshop proceedings is presented in the following Chapter. Annex A presents the Workshop agenda; Annex B shows the list of participants; and in Annex C all 12 presentation files can be found.

2. Workshop Summary

The GEMMA Online Workshop on Welding technologies for Generation IV systems, their qualifications and residual stress modelling was organised by the European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC), Petten, the Netherlands, on 4 and 5 October 2021.

Day 1

The Workshop was opened, and participants welcomed by Concetta Fazio, Head of the Nuclear Reactor Safety and Emergency Preparedness Unit of the JRC. She provided a brief overview of the GEMMA project and its key objectives. She also explained that the Workshop is a part of the dissemination activity of the project, including in particular partners of the European Network on Neutron Techniques Standardization for Structural Integrity (NeT).

An overview of the GEMMA project was then provided by the GEMMA project coordinator, P. Agostini from ENEA. The main objective of the GEMMA project is to enhance the maturity of materials and material solutions (existing and innovative) for Generation IV applications. In this context, four European Generation IV fast neutron spectrum reactor concepts were considered in GEMMA: (i) ASTRID (sodium-cooled); (ii) ALFRED (lead-cooled); (iii) MYRRHA (lead-bismuth eutectic cooled); and (iv) ALLEGRO (helium cooled). The work of the GEMMA project is based on three mutually complementary and reinforcing pillars: (i) materials characterizations; (ii) materials modelling; and (iii) development & qualification of innovative materials. The main materials of interest were 316-grade steels, i.e., A3.1S and A3.3S materials as specified in the RCC-MRx Code.

Session 1 of the Workshop discussed aspects related to weld manufacturing and characterisations. The Session included two technical presentations from G. Barbieri (ENEA, Italy) and M. Serrano (CIEMAT, Spain).

The first technical contribution of Session 1, given by G. Barbieri, dealt with weld manufacturing technologies for Generation IV systems, describing also manufacturing of austenitic stainless steel 316L-grade welded coupons. These were fabricated, using the Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) and Submerged Arc Welding (SAW) processes, by an industrial partner (Walter Tosto). In addition, the manufacturing of experimental welds of 15/15 Ti-steel was also discussed.

The second technical presentation of M. Serrano reported on outcomes of weld characterisation mechanical tests in air and inert environments. Slow strain rate tensile, fracture toughness, creep, and micro-hardness properties were analysed together with the accompanying microstructural properties. Among others, it has been demonstrated that tensile properties of the investigated 316L-grade materials are in accordance with RCC-MRx specifications up to the temperature of 400°C. In the frame of GEMMA, small tensile specimen technique was also developed for the testing of samples from thin plates of 15/15 Ti-steel.

Session 2 was dedicated to aspects related to the weld qualification and codification for fast Generation IV systems.

The Session was introduced by a keynote speech of C. Pétesch (CEA), explaining weld qualification requirements for Generation IV systems as stipulated in the RCC-MRx Code. After

the introductory discussion of the RCC-MRx Code and its structure, the particular attention was dedicated to Section III, and there specifically Volume 4 of the Code that addresses requirements for welding. In this context, the presentation discussed first the requirements to be fulfilled prior to the welding. This involves the demonstration of the weldability of the chosen base material, the technical qualification of the selected welding procedure, welders and production workshop, as well as the qualification & acceptance of the chosen filler material. In addition, specificities regarding RCC-MRx code requirements for Generation IV systems were discussed. This concerns in particular long-term operation in high-temperature conditions (>375°C for stainless steels). Under these conditions, creep resistance and thermal ageing need to be specifically taken into account. Additionally, it was pointed out that corrosion and any possible other environmentally induced damage have to be carefully considered. It was further concluded that for materials of a wider interest for Gen-IV systems, welded joint properties are largely missing. This is possibly with the exception of materials considered for sodium-cooled fast reactors (SFRs), as SFRs specifically benefit from knowledge gained through the R&D work associated with the construction and operation of Phénix and SuperPhénix SFRs in France. The main objective of the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) Workshop 64 (WS64), Prospective Group 2 (PG2) on “Mechanics GEN IV and innovative reactors” is to identify the corresponding gaps in the RCC-MRx Code. To fill the identified gaps, the CEN WS64 PG2 further develops corresponding R&D and code evolution proposals.

The subsequent technical contribution of H.-Y. Lee (KAERI, Republic of Korea) reviewed elevated temperature design rules for welded joints in the ASME Code and compared them comprehensively to those in the RCC-MRx Code. In addition, capabilities of the KAERI-developed HITEP software platform to perform reliable integrity evaluations of welded joints in accordance with ASME and RCC-MRx were presented. The presentation also gave several examples of the application of the HITEP in design of large-scale experimental test loops with sodium coolant at KAERI.

The third presentation of Session 2 – given by K.-F. Nilsson (JRC, the Netherlands) – specifically analysed gaps and further development needs of the RCC-MRx Code for heavy liquid metal (HLM) cooled reactors. In this context, while recognising that further experimental data would be needed before drawing robust conclusions, it was concluded that there are no indications of liquid metal embrittlement of the studied candidate materials for the Gen-IV HLM-cooled reactor concepts. A need for harmonized test procedures and standards to reduce the scatter in the generated experimental data was additionally emphasised.

Day 2

The second day of the Workshop was opened by Kamil Tuček (JRC), coordinator of Work Package 2 of the GEMMA project. He welcomed the participants and explained that the presentations in Sessions 3 and 4 would focus on welding residual stresses (WRS), their measurement and prediction by numerical simulations, and on the consideration of these stresses in component integrity assessment codes. In order to address the latter aspect, the workshop organizers had solicited presentations from members of the NeT European Network, who have some experience with WRS assessments and their translation into input to the UK R6 defect assessment code.

The first presentation in Session 3 was given by R.C. Wimpory from Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB, Germany). He gave a short overview of the available techniques for measurement of residual stresses. A considerable number of techniques is available to engineers to choose from. The most important families of techniques would be the diffraction techniques and the strain relaxation techniques. The techniques have different capabilities and the presentation gave an overview of criteria that one might consider when selecting a technique. Dr. Wimpory gave several examples of work that had been done at the HZB with neutron and X-ray diffraction techniques, and he showed how several techniques can be jointly implemented to complement each other when a problem requires a range of capabilities not offered by a single technique.

This was followed by a presentation by R. Coppola from ENEA-Casaccia (Italy) showing high-resolution neutron diffraction stress measurements on a narrow-gap tungsten inert gas welded (NG-TIG) coupon from GEMMA Task 2.3. These measurements had been carried out at the research reactor FRM-II in Garching (Germany). The results showed tensile residual stresses in the welding longitudinal direction reaching yield level, i.e., around 400 MPa, in and around the fusion zone of this coupon. In the transverse direction, lower stress levels were observed, and these stresses changed from tensile to compression through the thickness of the specimen. High tensile stresses were identified as a possible primary concern for component integrity. Dr. Coppola also discussed planning for measurements of stresses in this NG-TIG welded component after post-weld heat treatment to be accomplished later in October 2021.

C. Ohms (JRC) gave the next presentation where he introduced the activities of the NeT European Network on Neutron Techniques Standardization for Structural Integrity. This Network has been active for almost 20 years and its members/contributors predominantly work on WRS assessment by measurement and numerical simulation. The NeT investigates “simple” model cases of nuclear welds in a variety of nuclear structural materials, e.g., austenitic stainless steels (grade 316), ferritic steels and nickel base alloys. In recent years, NeT has also embarked on an activity with a dissimilar metal weld – nickel base consumable in a base plate from ferritic steel, and on an activity addressing additive manufacturing using austenitic stainless steel as base material and as weld consumable. The NeT has probably produced some of the most comprehensive WRS round robin exercises in existence and to this day, the Network has produced around 100 scientific publications and contributed to about 10 PhD theses.

M. Smith from the University of Manchester (UK) proceeded with a presentation on the lessons learned from the NeT about measuring and predicting residual stresses and then using them to predict crack driving forces. He used the example of NeT Task Group 4. The object of this Task Group’s investigations was an austenitic stainless steel (grade 316 L) plate with three matching weld beads deposited in a finite length slot in its middle. More than 10 measurements had been performed on these specimens, producing a robust average of the residual stress distribution, but showing at the same time that measurement outliers are very possible and they are often not easily recognizable as outliers. Therefore, it is required in R6 defect assessments to validate residual stress simulations by at least two independent measurements in order to be allowed to use these in the assessment. A similar situation was identified for the simulations. Prof. Smith pointed out the importance of reliable processes and of the expertise of the engineers involved. The correct choice of the process and material parameters, including for weld material, is of utmost importance. Several Task Groups of the NeT, including Task Group 4, have shown that the choice of hardening model is one of the

parameters of very high significance. The presentation concluded with an overview on how stress intensity factors derived from the measurement averages compare to those derived from simulations. Also here, it was shown how important the adequate selection of the simulation parameters is for obtaining a useable result.

Session 4 was opened with a presentation given by D. Gonçalves from CEA (France) on the numerical simulation of welding residual stresses in plate shaped stainless steel grade 316L(N) coupons manufactured by CEA for the GEMMA project. At the beginning, he pointed out that currently welding simulations cannot be used to fulfil RCC-MRx code requirements, as the code is not taking simulation results into account. Dr. Gonçalves then proceeded with an overview of the general process steps for a WRS simulation before introducing the welding process addressed in this case. CEA had manufactured four plates of 400 mm length, 300 mm width, and 24 mm thickness each, with a narrow-gap configuration tungsten inert gas (NG-TIG) weld implemented to join two halves of either plate with 11 weld beads deposited over the thickness. The weld simulations of the NG-TIG welded specimen consisted of a thermal analysis and a subsequent mechanical analysis. A metallurgical assessment was not considered, as this austenitic stainless steel is not undergoing high temperature phase transformations. It was shown how the thermal results were validated by the good comparison of the predicted temperature evolutions in the coupons with corresponding temperature records taken during the welding process. One of the most important parameters in the mechanical assessment in such cases is often the selected constitutive law. CEA had chosen a Chaboche elastoplastic model with mixed strain hardening, where they could achieve a good agreement between a cyclic test on a 316L material and the corresponding numerical prediction of the stress-strain cycles. Dr. Gonçalves explained that they had implemented an annealing temperature of 1000°C in the mechanical analysis, meaning that the plastic history of a material section would be erased every time this section exceeds this limit. The analysis also took into account the clamping conditions of the plates during welding, where the plates were prevented from movements at either side of the plate by rigid mechanical constraints. To validate the results obtained, the residual stresses in the welding longitudinal direction were compared against corresponding measurement results obtained by the contour method at Aalto University (Finland), and against benchmarking computations covering the same coupons by the University of Nottingham (UK) and RATEN ICN (Romania). The good general agreement of the results suggested that adequate procedures and input data had been selected to achieve a sufficiently reliable prediction of the welding residual stresses.

The final presentation in this workshop was again given by M. Smith from the University of Manchester. He showed how the UK R6 defect assessment procedure takes into account welding residual stresses. Many components with welds need to be assessed either in the context of the basic safety case of the plant/component or because of defects found during operation. The R6 procedure is used in the UK when integrity assessments of structures/components with defects are required. The structure of the procedure was presented and the sections where WRSs are concerned were highlighted. Section III of the code contains a subsection addressing the calculation of WRSs. The purpose of being able to use (quasi-) realistic, simulated WRS distributions is to avoid the use of conservative upper bound profiles otherwise prescribed that can lead to overly conservative design or inspection choices. Stringent procedures are prescribed for such simulations; among others, validation of numerical predictions with residual stress measurements is necessary. Three levels of validation are defined and to be used in accordance with the severity of the issue to be addressed. The highest level would involve dedicated mock-ups to perform WRS

measurements on. Prof. Smith listed a few sample cases of existing studies that have been included in R6 section V for benchmarking purpose. These include NeT Task Groups 1 and 4, while the use of NeT Task Group 5 for this section is still under development. He finally explained how the derived WRS distributions would be used in the actual integrity assessment in accordance with the code provisions. The presentation concluded with the remark that the R6 procedure is still subject to further development, and several topics, e.g. residual stresses in steels subject to phase transformation, were pointed out.

The Workshop was concluded with a brief summary of C. Ohms and wrap-up of C. Fazio. She thanked all the presenters and participants for their valuable contributions to the successful Workshop, and closed the event.

3. Conclusion

As a dissemination activity within the GEMMA Project, this Workshop was a highly successful event. The activities within Work Package 2 were comprehensively presented and the first conclusions from the obtained results were drawn. The presenters also pointed out the knowledge gaps remaining in the various subject areas of this Work Package. The inclusion of contributions “external” to GEMMA, i.e., in relation to the RCC-MRx code itself, and from members of the NeT European Network have been of significant added value.

Several attendees have approached the organizers subsequent to the event with requests for further information and interest in future involvement in related activities.

Annex A – Workshop Agenda

GEMMA Online Workshop on Welding technologies for Generation-IV systems, their qualifications and residual stress modelling

Monday-Tuesday, 4-5 October 2021

Organised by: European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Petten, The Netherlands

Agenda

Monday, 4 October 2021

09:30 Workshop opening and welcome (C. Fazio, JRC)

09:45 Overview of the GEMMA project (P. Agostini, ENEA)

Session 1 – Weld manufacturing and characterisations (Chair: P. Agostini)

10:05 Weld manufacturing technologies for Generation-IV systems (G. Barbieri, ENEA)

10:30 Weld characterisations for Generation-IV systems (M. Serrano, CIEMAT)

10:55 *Coffee break*

Session 2 – Weld qualification and codification (Chair: R. Wimpory)

11:10 *Keynote speech* - Weld qualification requirements for Generation-IV reactors in RCC-MRx code (C. Petesch, CEA/AFCEN)

11:55 High temperature design of welded joint for Generation-IV in ASME (H.-Y. Lee, KAERI)

12:20 Gap analysis and further development needs for Heavy Liquid Metal Reactors – based on GEMMA WP4: “Compatibility with heavy liquid metal and helium coolants” (K.-F. Nilsson, JRC)

12:45 Wrap-up of the first day (K.-F. Nilsson, JRC)

Tuesday, 5 October 2021

09:30 Day opening and welcome (K. Tucek, JRC)

Session 3 – Residual stress measurements (Chair: D. Goncalves)

09:35 Residual stress measurement techniques (R. Wimpory, HZB)

10:00 High-resolution neutron diffraction measurements (R. Coppola, ENEA)

10:25 Overview of the activities of the European Network on Neutron Techniques Standardization for Structural Integrity [NeT] (C. Ohms, JRC)

10:50 *Keynote speech* - Lessons learned in NeT on weld residual stress analysis – impact on safety, defect assessments, and codification (M.C. Smith, University of Manchester)

11:20 *Coffee break*

Session 4 – Residual stress modelling and safety/integrity assessments according to the code requirements (Chair: C. Ohms)

11:35 Residual stress modelling for component design and safety/integrity assessments (D. Gonçalves, CEA)

12:00 The treatment of welds and weld residual stresses in the R6 defect assessment procedure (M.C. Smith, University of Manchester)

Session 5 – Wrap-up and conclusions (Chair: C. Fazio)

12:25 Brief summary of the Workshop (C. Ohms)

12:35 General discussions and conclusions (All)

Annex B – List of Attendees

Name	Affiliation	Country
Pietro Agostini	ENEA	Italy
Vasileios Akrivos	University of Manchester	UK
Giuseppe Barbieri	ENEA	Italy
Steve Bate	Jacobs	UK
Carlo Cristalli	ENEA	Italy
Diogo Gonçalves	CEA	France
Roberto Coppola	ENEA	Italy
Viorel Deaconu	RATEN ICN	Romania
Concetta Fazio	JRC	EU
Gianclaudio Ferro	ENEA	Italy
Mike Fitzpatrick	Coventry University	UK
Rebecca Hernandez	CIEMAT	Spain
Michael Hofmann	Technical University of Munich	Germany
Muhammad Kashif Khan	Coventry University	UK
Mike Keavey	University of Manchester	UK
Hyeong-Yeon Lee	KAERI	R. of Korea
Mitchell Leering	Coventry University	UK
Amke Lescur	SCK•CEN	Belgium
Suo Li	formerly University of Nottingham	UK
Karl-Fredrik Nilsson	JRC	EU
Florian Obermeier	Framatome	Germany
Carsten Ohms	JRC	EU
Cécile Pétesch	CEA/AFCEN	France
Joana Rebelo Kornmeier	Technical University of Munich	Germany
Daniel Richter	Framatome	Germany
Marco Schmidt	Framatome	Germany
Marta Serrano	CIEMAT	Spain
Mike Smith	University of Manchester	UK
Erich Stergar	SCK•CEN	Belgium
Gyula Török	Centre for Energy Research	Hungary
Grégoire Trespeuch	Europe Technologies	France
Chris Truman	University of Bristol	UK
Kamil Tuček	JRC	EU
Anastasia Vasileiou	University of Manchester	UK
Robert Wimpory	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin	Germany
Tassos Youtsos	-	Greece
Xiang Zhang	Coventry University	UK

Annex C – Presentations

Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie,
l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile

GEMMA

Overview of GEMMA project

*GEMMA Online Workshop on Welding technologies for Generation-IV systems,
their qualifications and residual stress modelling*

Monday-Tuesday, 4-5 October 2021

Pietro Agostini ENEA

GEMMA means **GE**neration IV **MA**terials **MA**turity

The ambition of GEMMA is in the name itself:

- to bring to maturity the materials for GenIV prototypes in Europe, allowing a big step forward towards the next phase of design for the harsh environmental conditions of ESNII reactors.

Work packages

Technical work packages

WP1: Advanced corrosion mitigation strategies

WP2: Welding development and characterization

WP3: Irradiation effects: modelling and experiments

WP4: Compatibility with HLM and He coolant

Supporting work packages

WP5: Consortium management

WP6: Communication, dissemination and exploitation of results

Duration in years	4,5
Total number of deliverables to be issued	42
Total cost	6.3 M€
Total EU contribution	4 M€
Number of participants (including KAERI)	23
Number of participating countries	12
Total effort in men-months	699

The expected progresses by GEMMA towards the four concepts were respected. They were:

- For ASTRID. Development of **physical models of microstructure evolution under irradiation in austenitic alloys**. **Measurement of residual stresses in welded joints** representative of Astrid
- For MYRRHA and ALFRED. **Corrosion of austenitic steels in HLM** determining safe operating conditions in terms of time, temperature, oxygen content regarding corrosion. **Screening of materials with superior corrosion resistance**. **Mechanical effects of HLM exposure**
- For ALLEGRO. Evaluation of **effects on structural materials of typical operational conditions**, providing clearer bases for design

- The research approach of the EERA JPNM is based on **three pillars** connected to each other in a virtuous circle, namely:
 - **materials characterization**,
 - **materials modelling**
 - **development of innovative materials** (or fabrication processes).
- in GEMMA this three-fold approach is applied to address those most stringent issues currently related to materials for GenIV fast reactor prototypes in Europe

On web site <http://www.eera-jpnm.eu/gemma/> at Tools, three important management tools are present:

- JPNM Poll
- Project Management
- Web Conference

The general objective of GEMMA Project is to qualify and certify selected structural materials for the construction of Generation IV reactors, as envisaged within the European Sustainable Industrial Initiative (ESNII). The structural materials, to be considered for the GEMMA project, are those selected by the designers of the reactors. Their qualification means that their resistance under the exposure conditions of high temperature, highly corrosive environment and intense flux of fast neutrons, will be experimentally verified and/or numerically modelled. The applicability of materials to the reactors' construction implies also that relevant welded joints will be tested as well as corrosion protection treatments. Even the corrosion resistance of new Alumina Forming Alloy steels and surface treatments will be tested in representative conditions.

Coordinated by Pietro Agostini, [ENEA](#) (IT)

RELATED LINKS

- EERA
- JPNM
- INSPYRE
- M4F
- MatDB

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This tool enables the coordinator and the chairman of the «Governing Board» to **launch votations by remote procedure.** Its use is recognized and accepted by all partners within the GEMMA Consortium Agreement

The screenshot shows the JPNM Poll List web interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, About us, JPNM Participants, Documents, Events & News, Tools, and Contact us. The main content area displays a list of polls. The first poll is titled "Endorsement to the creation and composition of a Data Committee within the GEMMA project" and is dated 2019-06-07. The description of the poll is: "Dear members of the GEMMA governing board, As you probably already know, in view of the large amount of experimental data to be produced within WP2 and WP4 of GEMMA, the interested WP leaders advanced to the Executive Committee a request to identify a Data Committee of 5 persons from partner organizations to assist them during data evaluation, performing hence quality assurance tasks related to the data management in MatDB. The Executive Committee agreed with this request and selected 5 candidates who have very kindly agreed to contribute voluntarily to the activities of the GEMMA Data Committee (see attached document). Since the Data Committee was not originally included in the Grant Agreement, on behalf of the Executive Committee and in quality of chair of designated the governing board, I would like to ask you to endorse the creation and composition of the Data Committee of GEMMA. Attached you'll find a note that describes why the Data Committee should be established, its role and the list of the selected candidates together with a short profile. Best regards Lorenzo". The poll has two questions: "1. Do you endorse the creation of a Data Committee for the GEMMA project?" and "2. Do you approve the composition of the GEMMA Data Committee?". Both questions have 16 YES and 7 N/A votes. The interface also includes a "New Poll" button, a "How To Use" button, and an "Events & News" sidebar with recent events.

Endorsement to the creation and composition of a Data Committee within the GEMMA project 2019-06-07

Description: Dear members of the GEMMA governing board, As you probably already know, in view of the large amount of experimental data to be produced within WP2 and WP4 of GEMMA, the interested WP leaders advanced to the Executive Committee a request to identify a Data Committee of 5 persons from partner organizations to assist them during data evaluation, performing hence quality assurance tasks related to the data management in MatDB. The Executive Committee agreed with this request and selected 5 candidates who have very kindly agreed to contribute voluntarily to the activities of the GEMMA Data Committee (see attached document). Since the Data Committee was not originally included in the Grant Agreement, on behalf of the Executive Committee and in quality of chair of designated the governing board, I would like to ask you to endorse the creation and composition of the Data Committee of GEMMA. Attached you'll find a note that describes why the Data Committee should be established, its role and the list of the selected candidates together with a short profile. Best regards Lorenzo

Created by: Lorenzo Malerba

1. Do you endorse the creation of a Data Committee for the GEMMA project? YES: 16 N/A: 7

2. Do you approve the composition of the GEMMA Data Committee? YES: 16 N/A: 7

Events & News

14 June '19
Friday, 14:00 ★
Notice of temporary service disruption

17 June '19
Monday, 12:30 ★
MB meeting
Faculty of Physics, Warsaw University, Poland

18 June '19
Tuesday, 12:30
17th EERA JPNM Steering Committee meeting
Faculty of Physics, University of Warsaw, Poland

[More events / news >>](#)

1. This tool reports a «living» version of the GANTT Diagram of the whole project
2. This allows to check instantaneously the state of deliverables and
3. Allows to perform the certified approval process for GEMMA Deliverables

Through ADOBE
CONNECT and
recently through
ZOOM it was possible
to have video-
conferences among
partners as well as
projection of
PowerPoint
presentations

The project has 23 partners and the testing activities were shared among all while few partners supplied raw materials and coated specimens.

The intense transfer of materials among partners generated the initial delays in GEMMA

The additional effects of COVID 19 induced the governing board to ask a project amendment to gain six months extension up to November 2021

Interesting new observations: negligible corrosion @480°C

GEMMA

CV-Rez evidenced negligible corrosion of austenitic steels at 480°C, low oxygen, 2 m/s flowing Pb

316L 16000 h

TIG 316L 16000 h

SAW 316L 16000 h

15-15 Ti 16000 h

Interesting observations: Pb corrosion over welds is lower than over base material

GEMMA

the magnitude of the corrosion of TIG / SAW welds in term of depth of penetration, is low if compared to the corrosion observed for BM at the same time. The maximum dissolution attack is 41 μm for BM samples and reaches 18 and 30 μm for TIG and SAW samples respectively at 2000 h. After 5000 h, the observed maximum dissolution attack is 89 μm on BM samples and reaches 38 and 56 μm for TIG and SAW samples respectively.

Maximum and Average dissolution depth with standard deviation of 316L BM and welds in Pb at 480°C.

Interesting observations :No embrittling effect due to liquid Pb

GEMMA

The 316L base material doesn't seem to be affected at all by LME (Liquid Metal Embrittlement).

At the temperature of 400°C and with a strain rate of $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{s}^{-1}$ the tensile curves achieved in lead almost perfectly superpose to those obtained in air.

Increasing the temperature to 550°C and decreasing the strain rate to $5 \times 10^{-6} \text{s}^{-1}$ the steel is even affected by increased ductility

Interesting observations: Coated steels and AFA are able to mitigate corrosion

GEMMA

PLD Alumina coating confirmed its superior protective action on 15-15 Ti at 550°C, low oxygen, flowing Pb after 4000 h

AFA 6 and AFA 9 show low corrosion (2-5 μm)

Naked 15-15 Ti

Naked 15-15 Ti weld

15-15 Ti PLD

316L pack cem.

AFA 6

Interesting achievement: steel corrosion mechanism by Pb

GEMMA

The outer oxide has a complex structure.

The inner Iron Chromium oxide provides channels for oxygen entering and iron leaching

At higher T, Lead is able to wet magnetite and the transport mechanisms are efficient

At lower T, the transport mechanisms are impeded

Pietro Agostini

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0101 0010 1101
0001 0110 1110
1101 0010 1101
1111 1010 0000

Italian National Agency for New Technologies,
Energy and Sustainable Economic Development

Weld manufacturing technologies for Generation-IV systems

GEMMA Online Workshop on Welding technologies for Generation-IV systems, their qualifications and residual stress modelling

Session 1 – Weld manufacturing and characterisations

4th October

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- Overview of main components
- Selected Welding technology
- Welding of SS 316 coupons
- Welding of 15-15 Ti coupons
- Conclusion

Overview of main components

ALFRED Primary System Overview

The main material candidates for the primary of ALFRED are reported in following Table:

Primary Thermal Cycle 1° stage	390-430°C
Materials 1° Stage	Internal structures: AISI 316L Cladding 15-15 Ti

P. Lorusso, "GEN-IV LFR Development: Status & Perspectives," *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, vol. 105, p. 318–331, 2018.

Overview of main components

GEMMA

ALFRED REACTOR OVERVIEW of operating temperature and thickness of the welds

Parameter	Value
Inner diameter	8300 [mm]
Height	10000
Vessel thickness	50
Vessel Y joint thickness	85
Skirt Y joint thickness	85
Skirt straight joint thickness	50

**First question!
What means
AISI 316 L?**

What For DESIGNER:
AISI 316L means in terms of BM
Features of: A3.3S Appendix 9
X2CrNiMo17-12-2 (1,4404)
X2CrNiMo17-12-3 (1,4432)
X2CrNiMo18-14-3 (1,4435)

A3.3S Properties Group relate to austenitic stainless steel containing chromium-nickel and molybdenum with no special checking of the nitrogen content. The grade is also supplied and used deep-quenched from a temperature in the region of 1050°C. Its properties are the subject of Appendix **A3.3S** with a lower level than **A3.1S** of the tensile and creep properties. Minimum values of mechanical properties provided as a function of temperature by the European standards for use on pressure vessels have been taken into account in this Properties Group. In the case of other properties, such as ductility and the effects of irradiation, it is not possible to distinguish between the grades of austenitic stainless steel containing chromium nickel and molybdenum with and without nitrogen content control.

CONTENTS

Section III – Tome 1 – Subsection Z – Appendix A3.3S:
Properties Groups for products and parts
in X2CrNiMo17-12-2, X2CrNiMo17-12-3, X2CrNiMo18-14-3
solution annealed austenitic stainless steels

Table A3.3S.41: values of $R_{p0.2}$, R_m , S_m and S

Temperature (°C)	Products and parts in X2CrNiMo17-12-2, X2CrNiMo17-12-3, X2CrNiMo18-14-3 solution annealed austenitic stainless steels and RM 032, RM 033, RM 034 and RM 035 And Cast parts according to RM 341-2						Cast parts in GX2CrNiMo19-11-2 according to EN 10213 and NF A 32-060 (in accordance with RM 031)				
	$R_{p0.2min}$ (MPa)	$R_{p0.2moy}$ (MPa)	R_{mmin} (MPa)	R_{moy} (MPa)	S_m (MPa)	S (MPa)	$R_{p0.2min}$ (MPa)	$R_{p0.2moy}$ (MPa)	R_{mmin} (MPa)	S_m (MPa)	S (MPa)
	20	190	235	480	520	127	123	195	244	440	130
100	165	196	430	470	127	119	150	188	386	129	107
150	150				127	114					
200	137	159	390	430	123	108	120	150	350	108	97
250	127				114	107	105	132	346	95	89
300	113	135	380	423	102	102					
350	99	126	380	423	89	89					
400	97	120	380	423	87	87					
450	93	115	370	420	84	84					
500	89	110	360	411	80	80					
550	86	106	350	388	77	77					

CONTENTS

Section III – Tome 1 – Subsection Z - Appendix A9:
Properties Groups for welded joints

X2CrNiMo17-12-2 X2CrNiMo17-12-3 X2CrNiMo18-14-3	RM 332-1, RM 332-2 RM 333-2, RM 334-2 RM 334-5 EN 10028-7 EN 10222-5 EN 10272	A3.3S	19Cr12Ni2Mo RS 2925	Covered electrode	RS 3200	1	1.25	Not supplied
			19Cr12Ni2Mo RS 2915	Inert gas (TIG)	RS 3200	1	1.25	Not supplied
			19Cr12Ni2Mo RS 2945	Submerged arc	RS 3200	1	1.25	Not supplied
			Without	Electron beam	RS 3560	1	later	-

Materials understanding

What about welding and corrosion:
 X2CrNiMo17-12-2 (1,4404) X2CrNiMo17-12-3
 (1,4432) X2CrNiMo18-14-3 (1,4435)
 Note that RCC- MRx take as reference EN norms
 usually with additional requirements
 i.e: the specification for all type of semyfinished
 product are prescribed

Element	EN 10088-3 2005	RCC-MRx 332-2.31
S	<0.045	<0.030
P	<0.030	<0.015
Cu	Not required (NR)	<1
Co	NR	Depend on cobalt purity class
B	NR	<0.0018 for material to be welded

	C max	Si max	Mn max	P max	S max	Cr	Mo	Ni	N max	Cu max	B max
GEMMA Steel	0,03	1	2	0,03	0,015	16,5-19,0	2-3	10-15	0,10	1	0,0018
X2CrNiMo17-12-2	0,03	1	2	0,045	0,03	16,5-18,5	2-2,5	10-13	0,1	-	-
X2CrNiMo17-12-3	0,03	1	2	0,045	0,03	16,5-18,5	2,5-3	10,5-13	0,1	-	-
X2CrNiMo18-14-3	0,03	1	2	0,045	0,03	17-19	2,5-3	12,5-15	0,10	-	-
WT316 LN (N) IG 75 mm Acelor Mittal L4995	0,026	0,39	1,69	0,025	0,001	17,45	2,47	12,29	0,077	0,14	0,0007
30 mm Outo KUMPO 121584	0,018	0,53	1,11	0,023	0,001	17,18	2,52	12,55	0,036	0,10	0,0003
WT316 LN (N) IG 40mm Acelor Mittal S0196	0,025	0,42	1,73	0,019	0,001	17,64	2,38	12,10	0,069	0,12	0,0007

Base materials allowed 316L....could have
 Cr: 16,5 to 19%
 Ni: 10 to 15%
 Mo: 2 to 3%
 This in terms of corrosion strenght in liquidn Lead
 can change the performance

Materials understanding

About procedure of welding and filler materials do not change nothing

Table A9.GEN.11b: Properties Group to be used for welded joints - (Creep conditions)

Base metal: grade	Base metal: Reference Procurement Specification or standard	Base metal: Properties Group	Filler metal: grade Reference Data Sheet	Process	Welding procedure: qualification	Welded joint : Properties Group
X10CrMoVNb9-1	RM 242-2, RM 243-2, RM 244-2	A3.18AS	Mod9Cr RS 2721 (later)	TIG	RS 3200 + RS 3900	A9.J18AS
			Mod9Cr RS 2721 (later)	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	A9.J18AS
X2CrNiMo17-12-2 (N)	RM 332-1, RM 332-3, RM 333-1, RM 334-1, RM 334-2, RM 334-4, RM 334-5, RM 334-6, RM 334-7, RM 334-8	A3.1S	19Cr12Ni2Mo RS 2711.1	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	A9.J1S
			16Cr8Ni2Mo RS 2711.2	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	A9.J1S
			19Cr12Ni9Mo RS 2712.1 (later)	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			16Cr8Ni2Mo RS 2712.2	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr12Ni2Mo RS 2713.1	Submerged arc	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			16Cr8Ni2Mo RS 2713.2	Submerged arc	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
X2CrNiMo17-12-2 X2CrNiMo17-12-3 X2CrNiMo18-14-3	RM 332-2, RM 332-5, RM 333-2, RM 333-3, RM 333-5, RM 334-1, RM 334-2, RM 334-5, RM 334-6, RM 334-7, RM 334-8, RM 335-2, NF EN 10028-7, NF EN 10222-5, NF EN 10272	A3.3S	19Cr12Ni2Mo RS 2711.1	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	A9.J3S
			16Cr8Ni2Mo RS 2711.2	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	A9.J3S
			19Cr12Ni9Mo RS 2712.1 (ult.)	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			16Cr8Ni2Mo RS 2712.2	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr12Ni2Mo RS 2713.1	Submerged arc	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			16Cr8Ni2Mo RS 2713.2	Submerged arc	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied

Welding technology	Creep domain	RS data Sheet name	C	Si max	Mn	P max	S max	Cr	Mo	Ni	Co max	δ Ferrite
TIG ³	Negligible creep	RS2915	0-0,03	0,6	1-2,5	0,025	0,02	18-20	2-3	12-14	0,20	5-15
	Significant creep	RS 2712.2 (not standard)	0,03-0,045	0,5	1,8-2,5	0,025	0,02	16-17	1,8-2,5	8-9	0,20	3-7
SAW	Negligible creep	RS 2945	0-0,3	1,0	1-2,5	0,025	0,025	17-20	2-3	11-14	0,2	5-15
	Significant creep	RS 2713.1	0,03-0,045	0,7	1,2-2,0	0,025	0,02	18-19	2-2,3	11-12	0,20	3-7
		RS 2713.2	0,03-0,045	0,5	1,8-2,5	0,025	0,02	16-17	1,8-2,5	8-9	0,20	3-7

•Filler wire (1mm) - RS2915 Delta ferrite : 7%

TIG	C	Si	Mn	P	S*	Cr	Mo	Ni	Co	N*	Nb	Cu
THERMANIT GE-316L	0,012	0,42	1,72	0,018	0,009	18,33	2,53	12,17	0,04	0,05	0,02	0,12

•Filler wire (3,2 mm) - RS2945 Delta ferrite: 8% / 11% of the Flux

SAW	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Mo	Ni	Co	N	Nb	Cu
THERMANIT GE-316L	0,015	0,43	1,69	0,015	0,005	18,82	2,50	12,29	0,02	0,047	0,016	0,05
AVESTA FLUX 805	0,015	0,55	1,34	0,016	0,006	19,49	2,48	12,16	0,03	0,053	0,013	

•NOTE: the filler material and WPS reference RS3200 are the same for A3.1S and A3.3S

Welding technologies

- TIG multipass semi automatic process on 30 and 40 mm th \rightarrow 15 and 80 mm qualified

Main welding parameters:

- HI (manual)/automatic = (1,6 kJ/mm)/3,2 kJ/mm
- Speed: (40 mm/min)/ 80 mm/min
- T interpass = 150°C (but typical below 100°C)

Welding technologies

- SAW multipass semi automatic process on 75 mm th → 50 to 150 mm qualified

Main welding parameters:

- HI automatic = 1,6 kJ/mm
- Speed:600 mm/min
- T interpass = 150°C (but typical below 100°C)

Welding technologies

- TIG Single pass on 3 mm th → 1,5-6 mm qualified

Main welding parameters:

- HI automatic = 0,41 kJ/mm (160A -15,5V)
- Speed:360 mm/min
- Gap 0
- Gas He + Ar

 <small>Agencia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile</small>		WELDING PROCEDURE SPECIFICATION acc. to EN 15614-1			Doc. n°/Doc. nr 141(2018)_01 Comm./Job GEMMA Data /Date 15- SEPT 2018 Em./fiss.		
Procedimento / Procedure Tipo / Type		141 -TIG Automatic			Qualif. Di supp. / Supporting (WPAR)		
Trattamento termico/ PWHT	Intervallo Temp. / Range temp. Tempo mant. / Time range Grad. Riscald. / Heat rate Grad. Raffred. / Cool rate Altro / Other	n.a. - - -			Scizzo / Sketch 		
	Gas / Gas Plasma / Plasma Protezione / Shielding Aggiuntivo / Trailing Al rovescio / Backing Altro / Other	Tipo Type	Miscela % Mixture %	Portata Flow rate			
Tabella dati / Data chart	Passate o strati / Procedure di saldatura / Welding Procedure Runs or Layer	Nome o class. / Class or trade name	Diametro / Diameter (mm)	Current Amperes	Campo di tensione / Volt range	Velocità di Saldatura / Travel speed Range (mm/min)	Altro / Other Dritto
	1*	141	none	n.a.	160	DCEN	360

Welding Procedure Qualification

•For ARC WELDING THE TOME 4 od f RCC-MRx take in account the IO 15614-2 level2 ad prescribe some additional test See RS 3200

Table 1 – Examination and testing of the test pieces

Test piece	Type of test	Extent of testing
Butt joint with full penetration - Figure 1 and Figure 2	Visual	100 %
	Radiographic or ultrasonic	100 %
	Surface crack detection	100 %
	Transverse tensile test	2 specimens
	Transverse bend test	4 specimens
	Impact test	2 sets
	Hardness test	required
	Macroscopic examination	1 specimen

The minimum dimension for qualification test coupons are 2 pc. 150 x 350 mm
 For 316 L We choose to weld pcs 200 x 1000 mm
 30; 40 mm by NG TIF semiautomatic (WT proprietary WPS)
 75 mm By NG SAW fully mechanized (WT developed WPS for GEMMA)

3 mm (not in compliance due to the 15-15 Ti aivalable)

- 1 Discard 25 mm
- 2 Welding direction
- 3 Area for:
 - 1 tensile test specimen;
 - bend test specimens.
- 4 Area for:
 - impact and additional test specimens if required.
- 5 Area for:
 - 1 tensile test specimen;
 - bend test specimens.
- 6 Area for:
 - 1 macro test specimen;
 - 1 hardness test specimen.

Mechanical Features of Welded Coupons

•Coupon 17502 TIG 30 mm th

Tensile Test and SSRT in air on Cross Weld GTAW17502 (121584) 30 mm					
Temperature [°C]	Yield strength (MPa)	Rm (MPa)	Standard	Dimension (mm)	Partner
22	405-407	568-570	ISO 6892-1	a ₀ =2; b ₀ =12.5 L ₀ =50	RATEN
	385-495	604-619	ASTM G129	d ₀ =4.5; L ₀ =20	ENEA
	455-483	638-641		d ₀ =9; L ₀ =25	KAERI
350	255	416	ISO 6892-2	a ₀ =2; b ₀ =12.5 L ₀ =50	RATEN
400	285-385	461-476	ASTM G129	d ₀ =4.5; L ₀ =20	ENEA
450	381-390	501-506		d ₀ =9; L ₀ =25	KAERI
	370-382	494-499		d ₀ =9; L ₀ =25	KAERI
550	209	337	ISO 6892-2	a ₀ =2; b ₀ =12.5 L ₀ =50	RATEN
	267-334	403-423	ASTM G129	d ₀ =4.5; L ₀ =20	ENEA

^a₀ original thickness; ^b₀ original width; ^d₀ original diameter; ^L₀ original gauge length

Transversal Tensile Test

Filler material	Designation	Process	Reference Data Sheet			
Solid wire	16Cr8Ni2Mo (Non standard)	TIG 141	RS 2712.2			
3.1.4 Tensile test (transversal) (RS 3234.1)						
Base metal	Weld condition	Room	200°C (3)	450°C (3)	550°C (3)	
		R _m	R _m	R _m	R _m	
X2CrNiMo17-12-2 with controlled nitrogen content	As welded	≥ 525 MPa	≥ 425 MPa		≥ 380 MPa	
X2CrNiMo17-12-2 with controlled nitrogen content	DSHT (See §5 hereunder)	≥ 525 MPa			≥ 340 MPa	
X2CrNiMo17-12-2, X2CrNiMo17-12-3 and X2CrNiMo18-14-3	As welded	≥ 520 MPa			≥ 350 MPa	
X2CrNi19-10 with controlled nitrogen content	As welded	≥ 510 MPa		≥ 390 MPa		
X2CrNi19-11	As welded	≥ 500 MPa		≥ 345 MPa		

Mechanical Features of Welded Coupons

•Coupon 17502 TIG 30 mm th

Tensile Test in air on Weld GTAW17502 (121584) 30 mm					
Temperature [°C]	Yield strength (MPa)	Rm (MPa)	Standard	Dimension (mm)	Partner
22	429	535	ISO 6892-1	a ₀ =2; b ₀ =12.5 L ₀ =50	RATEN
350	421	465			
550	222	360			

¹a₀ original thickness; b₀ original width; d₀ original diameter; L₀ original gauge length

1.3 Mechanical tests									
1.3.1 Tensile test (longitudinal) (RS 2536)									
Temperature	Room			200°C (3)			550°C (3)		
	R _{p0.2}	R _m	A	R _{p0.2}	R _m	A	R _{p0.2}	R _m	A
Flat position test plate	≥ 350 MPa	≥ 550 MPa	≥ 35 %	(1)	≥ 425 MPa	(1)	(1)	≥ 380 MPa	≥ 20%

(1) Measurement for information purposes; (3) Temperature chosen according the specified use.

Tensile Test on welds (Longitudinal Tnsile Test)

Mechanical Features of Welded Coupons

GEMMA

•Coupon SAW17502 75mm th

ID. SAGGIO Identification test		DIMENSIONE PROVETTA Specimen size			CARICO DI ROTTURA Tensile strenght						
PROVA Test No.	SENSO Direction	SPESS. Thick. mm	LARGH. Width mm	AREA Area mm	FM N	RM N/mm ² ≥ 525 ≤ 670	Posizione di rottura Location of fracture		Aspetto della frattura Fracture appearance		Temp. °C
							In saldatura In weld	Fuori saldatura Out weld	Duttile Ductile	Fragile Fragile	
229AT1	T	20,38	25,02	509,9	285701	560		X	X		22
229AT2	T	20,06	25,04	502,3	288171	574		X	X		22
229AT3	T	20,30	25,06	508,7	286764	564		X	X		22
229AT4	T	18,17	24,98	453,9	280889	619		X	X		22
229AT5	T	18,44	25,03	461,6	258424	560		X	X		22

SAGGIO Identification		DIMENSIONE PROVETTA Size			CARATTERISTICHE E RISULTATI DELLA PROVA DI PIEGA Features and bend test results				
Prova N. Test No.	Senso Direction	Spessore Thickness mm	Larghezza Width mm	Lunghezza Length mm	Tipo Type	Mandrino Former Ø mm	Dist.appoggi Roller dist. mm	Angolo Bend Angle	Risultato Result
229AB1	T	10,23	58,99	300	LATERALI SIDE	40	63	180	Assenza di difetti Absence of defects
229AB2	T	10,04	59,65	300	LATERALI SIDE	40	63	180	Assenza di difetti Absence of defects
229AB3	T	10,32	59,87	300	LATERALI SIDE	40	63	180	Assenza di difetti Absence of defects
229AB4	T	10,11	58,98	300	LATERALI SIDE	40	63	180	Assenza di difetti Absence of defects

ID. SAGGIO Identification test		DIMENSIONE PROVETTA Specimen size				SNERVAMENTO Yield strenght		ROTT. Tensile Strenght	ALLUNG. Elongation	STRIZ. Reduction	TEMP
PROVA N. Test No.	SENS. Direc.	DIAM. Diam. mm	LAR. Width mm	AREA Area mm ²	L0 mm	Rp 0,2 N/mm ² ≥ 220	Rp 1 N/mm ² ≥ 262	Rm N/mm ² ≥ 525 ≤ 800	A %	Z %	°C
229ATL1	L - Top	10,01	---	78,7	50	457	511	578	30	65	22
229ATL2	L - 1/2 thk	10,05	---	79,3	50	472	562	574	38	66	22

SAGGIO Test	VALORI Values	C%	Si%	Mn%	P%	S%	Cr%	Ni%	Mo%	Co%
WM TOP	Required	< 0,030	< 1,00	1,00-2,50	< 0,025	< 0,025	17,00-20,00	11,00-14,00	2,00-3,00	< 0,20
229ACA	Result	0,003	0,471	1,27	0,016	0,008	19,98	12,21	2,63	0,019
SAGGIO Test	VALORI Values	Ni eq.%	Cr eq.%	Ferrite%	---	---	---	---	---	---
WM TOP	Required	---	---	5,00-15,00	---	---	---	---	---	---
229ACA	Result	13,87	22,61	11,00	---	---	---	---	---	---

Mechanical Features of Welded Coupons

•Coupon SAW17502 GEMMA TRANSVERSAL TEST → NOTE

Tensile Test in air on Cross Weld
SAW17502 (L4995) 75 mm

Temperature [°C]	Yield strength (MPa)	Ultimate Tensile strength (MPa)	Standard	Dimension (mm)	Partner
22-24	436-446	603-625	ISO 6892-1	d ₀ =9; L ₀ =25	KAERI
	412	575		a ₀ =2; b ₀ =12.5 L ₀ =50	RATEN
	487-491	558-561		a ₀ =2; b ₀ =1.5 L ₀ =5.6	JRC
350	255	423	ISO 6892-2	a ₀ =2; b ₀ =12.5 L ₀ =50	RATEN
400	314-378	487-504	ISO 6892-2	d ₀ =9; L ₀ =25	KAERI
	382-401	445-452		a ₀ =2; b ₀ =1.5 L ₀ =5.6	JRC
550	222	355	ISO 6892-2	a ₀ =2; b ₀ =12.5 L ₀ =50	RATEN
	362-364	402-407		a ₀ =2; b ₀ =1.5 L ₀ =5.6	JRC

Filler material	Designation	Process	Reference Data Sheet
Solid wire associated with a flux	19Cr12Ni2Mo (Non standard)	Automatic arc 121	RS 2713.1

3.1.4 Tensile test (transversal) (RS 3234.1)

Base metal	Weld condition	Room	200°C (3)	450°C (3)	550°C (3)
		R _m	R _m	R _m	R _m
X2CrNiMo17-12-2 with controlled nitrogen content	As welded	≥ 525 MPa	≥ 425 MPa	≥ 400 MPa	
X2CrNiMo17-12-2 with controlled nitrogen content	DSHT (See §5 hereunder)	Ult.			
X2CrNiMo17-12-2, X2CrNiMo17-12-3 and X2CrNiMo18-14-3	As welded	≥ 520 MPa		≥ 350 MPa	
X2CrNi17-19-10 with controlled nitrogen content	As welded	≥ 510 MPa		≥ 390 MPa	
X2CrNi19-11	As welded	≥ 500 MPa		≥ 345 MPa	

Mechanical Features of Welded Coupons

•Coupon SAW17502 75mm th GEMMA Longitudinal in WELD

Tensile Test in air on Weld
SAW17502 (L4995) 75 mm

Temperature [°C]	Yield strength (MPa)	Ultimate Tensile strength (MPa)	Standard	Dimension (mm)	Partner
22-24	434-442	535-575	ISO 6892-1	a ₀ =2; b ₀ =12.5 L ₀ =50	RATEN
	464-472	528-543		a ₀ =2; b ₀ =1.5 L ₀ =5.6	JRC
350	314-341	363-369	ISO 6892-2	a ₀ =2; b ₀ =12.5 L ₀ =50	RATEN
400	352-267	429-446		a ₀ =2; b ₀ =1.5 L ₀ =5.6	JRC
550	239-243	312-314		a ₀ =2; b ₀ =12.5 L ₀ =50	RATEN
	327	378		a ₀ =2; b ₀ =1.5 L ₀ =5.6	JRC

•Some more investigation should be necessary because i.e in transversal test at 550°C RATEN recognize 355MPa and in Longitudinal 312-314MPa
•BUT NOTE THAT WE HAD USED STANDARD FILLER MATERIAL

1.3 Mechanical tests

1.3.1 Tensile test (longitudinal) (RS 2536)

Temperature	Room			200°C (3)					
	R _{p0.2}	R _m	A	R _{p0.2}	R _m	A			
Flat position test plate	≥ 340 MPa	≥ 540 MPa	≥ 35 %	(1)	≥ 425 MPa	≥ 20 %			
Temperature	450°C (3)			550°C (3)					
	R _{p0.2}	R _m	A	R _{p0.2}	R _m	A			
Flat position test plate	(1)	≥ 400 MPa	≥ 20 %	(1)	≥ 380 MPa	≥ 20 %			

15-15 Titanium for cladding

Target Chemical composition

Fe	C	Cr	Ni	Mn	Mo	Ti	Si	B
Bal	0.08 – 0.1	14.0-16.0	14.0-16.0	1.0-2.0	1.3-1.7	0.30-0.50	0.70-0.90	0.003-0.007
-	(0.1)	(14.5)	(14.5)	-	-	(Ti/4C)>1.0	(0.85)	(0.004)
P	Nb+Ta	N, S, Al, Zr, W, V, Cu, Co, Ca, Sb, Sn, O						
0.03-0.05	<0.03	As Low As Possible						
(0.045)	-							

Grain Size specification ASTM E112 STANDARD : $6 \leq G \leq 9$

Production Phases

1st STEP: Vacuum Induction Melting (VIM)

2nd STEP: Vacuum Arc Remelting (VAR)

3rd STEP: Hot rolling

4th STEP: COLD Rolling 20% of CW

15-15Ti: production

VIM

VAR

Machined for ROLLING

Hot rolled from 120mm to 25 mm
T= 1000 °C

Two Step of Cold working
1st STEP: 25 → 20 mm (20%)
Annealing 1150°C 5' + controlled Cooling up to 500°C
2nd STEP: 20 → 15 mm

15-15 Ti: mechanical features

Sigla provetta		Specimen ID	1515 Ti - A	1515 Ti - B	1515 Ti - C	MEDIE
Velocità deformazione fino a Rp, ReH, ReL (1/s)		Strain rate up to Rp, ReH, ReL	2.50E-04	2.50E-04	2.50E-04	2.50E-04
Velocità per Rm (1/s)		Strain rate for Rm	6.70E-03	6.70E-03	6.70E-03	6.70E-03
T (°C)	Temperatura di prova	Test temperature	RT	RT	RT	RT
do (mm)	Diametro Iniziale	Original diameter of the parallel length	8.92	8.92	8.88	8.91
So (mm2)	Sezione Iniziale	Original cross sectional area of the parallel length	62.49	62.49	61.93	62.39
Lo(mm)	Tratto Utile	Original gauge length	45	45	45	45
Le(mm)	Base Estensimetro	Extensometer gauge length	50	50	50	50
Fp 0,2 % (N)	Carico Scost. Prop.	Force corresponding to the proof strength, plastic extension 0.2%	45780	47615	45964	46233
Fmax (N)	Carico Massimo	Maximum force	52103	52514	51946	52305
Lu (mm)	Lunghezza Ultima	Final gauge length after fracture	53.19	52.82	53.19	52.81
du (mm)	Diametro Ultimo	Minimum diameter after fracture	5.75	5.62	5.67	5.66
Su (mm2)	Sezione Ultima	Minimum cross sectional area after fracture	25.97	24.81	25.25	25.19
Rp 0,2 % (MPa)	C. Unit. Sc. Prop.	Proof Strength, plastic extension 0.2%	733	762	742	746 ✓
Rm (MPa)	C. Unit. A Rottura	Tensile strength	834	840	839	838 ✓
A (%)	Allungamento Perc.	Percentage elongation after fracture	18,2	18,0	18,1	18,1 ✓
Z (%)	Strizione Perc.	Percentage reduction of area after fracture	58	60	59	60

Request:
 $R_m \geq 760 \text{ MPa}$
 $620 \leq R_{p0.02} \leq 840 \text{ MPa}$
 $A_{tot} \geq 18\%$

HV10	ID	1T	2T	3T	4
POSITION	1/2	267	274	276	263
	1/2	268	272	272	269
	1/2	271	265	277	270
	Mean	269	270	275	267

15-15Ti: Making coupons for welds

Plates 3 x 100 x 170 mm

15-15 Ti: Welding Parameters evaluation

GEMMA

FIXED: diameter of Electrode and Shape:

Diameter 3,2 mm; shape 120° ; type W-La;

Variable:

- Speed; Current; Voltage (depend on set-up: Distance and gases)
- Electrode distance 1mm-1,5 mm
- Process: gases (Ar, He, 50He+50Ar, 75Ar+20He+5H₂ “HydrostarT300[®]”)
- Distance between edge (GAP) (1-0,5-0,2)

Evaluation by:

- Visual & Macro;
- RX;
- Hardness;

GAP 1 mm Milled

GAP 0

GAP 0,2 Insert

Challenge: full penetration by TIG without filler wire

(not available to adjust the shape)

Session 1 – Weld manufacturing and characterisations

15-15Ti: Welding process development

Test with He:

Id.	Gap	Speed	Current	Distance	Gas	trail	Nozzle	Back	Macro
11a	T-T, 0.5mm	5mm/s	175A	1,5mm	He	30L	10L	10L	
11b	T-T, 0.5mm	5mm/s	150A	1,5mm	He	30L	10L	10L	
11c	T-T, 0	5mm/s	150A	1,5mm	He	30L	10L	10L	
11d	T-T, 0	6mm/s	150A	1,5mm	He	30L	20L	10L	

15-15Ti: Welding process development

Comparison with different Gases:

Id.	Gap	Speed	Current	Distance	Gas	trail	Nozzle	Back	Macro
11G	T-T 0	6mm/s	150A	1mm	He	30L	20L	10L	
11H	T-T 0	6mm/s	150A	1mm	Ar/He	30L	10L	10L	
11I	T-T, 0	6mm/s	200A	1mm	Ar/He	30L	10L	10L	
12a	T-T, 0	6 mm/s	180A	1 mm	<u>Idrostar</u> T300	30L	10L	10L	
12b	T-T, 0	6 mm/s	160A	1 mm	<u>Idrostar</u> T300	30L	10L	10L	

11H: not fully penetration guaranty

111 like in Visual Analysis show some deposit (Dark zone)

Microstructures evaluation

FZ > 8 mm
HAZ ≈ 3mm

HV0.5: BM ≈ 300 ± 10
FZ ≈ 155 ± 5

15-15Ti: preliminary features

Several welding coupons were realized and sent to partner of Project GEMMA:
Tensile Test and Creep test are ongoing

Coupon 13 (B,C,D,E,F)

COUPONS: 12H & 13A

Coupon 14 (A,B,C,D,E)

SSRT in air on BASE & transversal weld SS15-15 Ti (VR 021-026) 3 mm						
Zone	Temper. [°C]	Yield strength (MPa)	Ultimate Tensile strength (MPa)	Standard	Dimension (mm)	Direction
Base metal	550	639-690	692-728	ISO 6892-2	$a_0=2; b_0=2$ $L_0=18$	(T)
		604-613	673-694		$a_0=2; b_0=2$ $L_0=18$	(L)
Weld	22	283-310	442-493		$a_0=1.5; b_0=2$ $L_0=9.8$	(TW)
	550	193-217	426-436		$a_0=2; b_0=2$ $L_0=18$	(TW)

First result of Tensile test confirm the High softening in FZ

1-The industrial process for welding GEN IV Nuclear Plant were been selected:

TIG NG and SAW are the main candidate for workshop production; electrode sure will be necessary for on site assembling but in a research project would have been difficult to manage considering that the results could be dependent from the operator skills;

2- The AISI 316 L could be a "too large" choice, even in compliance with RCC-MRx there are limits in terms of Cr, Ni and Mo that are wide.

So, if it is not a challenge in standard environment, in the liquid lead the corrosion features could be change significantly. The final data analyses on GEMMA project could give interesting information to evaluate the updating of requirement for the 316 L chemistry for some component of the GEN IV plants;

3- Different specimens shape and rules were adopted to evaluate mechanical and corrosion strength. This give some data scattering that need to be analyzed, justified, and in some cases discharged because have not sense (see Ry in transversal Tensile Test).

4- TIG welding of 3 mm th 15-15-Ti plates is a study of the worst possible condition in welded components. It could be provide interesting data but at the moment is a study not an assessment because the material is available in THICK plates that are not usually for final components (usual pipes of not more than 1 mm thick)

5- It is necessary to reanalyze all the data now available even in terms of corrosion to a complete evaluation.

Further development:

Considering the operating temperature of GEN IV are over 375°C , on the basis and with the experience of GEMMA, a new project using the not standard filler material for creep condition could be a good way to assess completely the Welding material and processes.

In this case:

- NEED a Steel Maker Partner;
- NEED a filler material Partner

Acknowledgement to the GEMMA : GEneration IV Materials Maturity - PROJECT

Grant Agreement N°: 755269

Thank You

EUROPEAN COMMISSION
DIRECTORATE-GENERAL RESEARCH & INNOVATION
Energy
Fission Energy

GEMMA

Titolo della presentazione - Luogo e data

Weld characterisations for Generation-IV systems

Marta Serrano, Rebeca Hernández
(CIEMAT)

*GEMMA Online Workshop on Welding technologies for Generation-IV
systems, their qualifications and residual stress modelling
Monday-Tuesday, 4-5 October 2021*

Contents

- Austenitic stainless steel welds
- GEMMA testing results
- Summary

Austenitic stainless steel welds

- Excellent summary of existing data on tensile and fracture toughness of SS weld can be found at NUREG/CR-6428, Rev. 1 (Omesh K. Chopra August 2018)

Austenitic stainless steel welds

- The overall fracture toughness of austenitic SS welds is controlled by the density and morphology of the second phase particles and to some extent on the ferrite content of the weld.
- The fracture toughness of welds is generally lower than that of wrought or cast SSs because of the higher density of inclusions.
- It depends on the weld process and not the composition

- Gas tungsten arc (GTA) welds exhibit the highest toughness
- Shielded metal arc (SMA) welds have intermediate toughness;
- and submerged arc (SA) welds have the lowest toughness

Austenitic stainless steel welds

- Austenitic stainless steel weld metal contains a dispersion of δ ferrite in austenite (3-9%) to overcome hot cracking
 - δ ferrite acts as strengthened \rightarrow tensile properties of welds are similar to 7-8% CW base metal
 - δ ferrite content is a function of the chemical composition and the welding process history

Figure 6. SEM micrographs of (a) schematic representation of welded joint; (b) weld metal; (c) heat-affected zone (HAZ) and (d) base metal.

- Because the ferrite phase is brittle at low temperatures, austenitic SS welds also exhibit a ductile-brittle transition temperature (DBTT) phenomenon.
- However, at ambient and elevated temperatures, the ferrite phase shows a ductile deformation behaviour

GEMMA Task 2.2

- The objective of Task 2.2 is to perform weld qualification tests, conduct reference mechanical tests in air, and characterise microstructure of specimens from reference welds (coupons).
- The activities include, for each welding process, material, and thickness (as relevant):

GTAW/TIG 316L WELD
SAW 316L WELD
TIG 15/15Ti WELD

Weld qualification mechanical tests in air according to RCC-MRx, including longitudinal tensile tests on base and weld material, transverse tensile tests on cross weld, bend tests (i.e., root, face, and side tests), Charpy tests (on base material, weld material, and cross weld), and hardening tests

Reference mechanical tests in air to be compared to those performed in HLM in task 4.2

- slow strain rate tensile,
- fracture toughness, and
- creep

Microstructural analysis:

- Evaluation of the grain structure and size
- δ -ferrite content
- Micro-hardness profile,
- Light optical microscopy (LOM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD), focused ion beam (FIB), X-ray tomography

GTAW/TIG 316L WELD - Microstructure

- GTAW 316L weld
 - Measurement of chemical composition by EDS (CVR)
 - Hardness (CVR, CIEMAT)
 - Optical microscopy (CVR)
- Relevant information:
 - The weld has a typical dendritic structure without pores and cracks
 - The textures which appeared after the Adler etching indicate that the L-BM and P-BM were likely rolled in different orientations (rotated 90°)

GTAW/TIG 316L WELD – Tensile (SSRT)

The yield strength of the weld is higher for the weld metal however; ultimate tensile strength is similar or smaller than the base metal.

GTAW/TIG 316L WELD – Fracture toughness

- No valid data can be obtained on the **Base Metal** due to the high ductility
- A large scatter on the results for the base metal can be observed and it cannot be attributed to the specimen size effect. A detailed examination of this results would be needed

GTAW/TIG 316L WELD – Fracture toughness

- KAERI->The J-R values of weld metal at RT and 450°C show that they are around half of those for base metal.

GTAW/TIG 316L WELD – Creep

SAW 316L WELD- Microstructure

- SAW 316L WELD
 - EBSD maps (JRC)
 - Hardness (CIEMAT)

SAW VS1 (weld) LOM (x50) RT	SAW VS3 (weld) LOM (x50) 350C	SAW VS5 (weld) LOM (x50) 550C

SAW 316L WELD- Tensile

- A comparison of the tensile properties between the base metal, transverse weld and longitudinal weld can be seen in the next figure. In general yield strength is higher for the weld in both orientations than for the base metal. In the case of the UTS values, no evident differences can be seen.

SAW 316L WELD- Tensile

- The yield strengths of TIG and SAW plate were higher at RT but similar at the temperatures of 400°C and 450°C when compared to those of KAERI plate. A clear plateau of TS is observed in the temperature range of 350°C and 550°C.

Tensile (SSRT) - SAW 316L WELD

Tensile uniaxial
JRC

Small punch fracture
CIEMAT

Tensile (SSRT) - SAW 316L WELD

- The J-R values of weld metal at RT and 450°C in SAW plate show that the J-R values dropped far more than for the TIG plate. Thus the reduction factor for the weld is larger for the SAW plate than for the TIG plate and also the absolute crack growth resistance is significantly lower for the SAW weld compared to the TIG weld.

Creep- SAW 316L WELD

- Small punch creep (JRC): The test results indicate that the as welded weld metal has reduced ductility compared to the base material

TIG 15/15Ti WELD- Microstructure

- TIG 15/15Ti WELD
 - OM (CIEMAT)
 - SEM (CIEMAT)
 - Hardness (CIEMAT, CVR)
 - Nanoindentation (CIEMAT)

Tensile (SSRT) – TIG 15/15Ti WELD

Tensile (SSRT) – TIG 15/15Ti WELD

Tensile uniaxial
CIEMAT

Small punch fracture
CIEMAT

Creep– TIG 15/15Ti WELD

- Small flat specimens were tested

Fracture toughness– TIG 15/15Ti WELD

- Fracture toughness has been determined by testing small specimens (CVR)

Summary

- An extensive testing campaign of three different welds has been carried out within GEMMA project
 - Preliminary testing at this stage of the project verifies that the required tensile properties of the base as weld metal up to a temperature of 400°C are in accordance with the RCC-MRx requirements.
 - The fracture toughness of welds are lower than for the BM as expected
 - Small specimens tests techniques has been developed to obtain tensile, creep and fracture toughness values
 - This results are used as reference value to assess the effect of liquid metal on the mechanical properties

Generation IV Materials Maturity (GEMMA)

The research leading to these results has been carried out in the frame of EERA Joint Programme on Nuclear Materials and is partly funded by the European Commission HORIZON 2020 Framework Programme under grant agreement No. 755269

GEMMA Online Workshop on Welding technologies for Generation-IV systems,
their qualifications and residual stress modelling
Monday-Tuesday, 4-5 October 2021

Weld qualification requirements for Generation-IV reactors in RCC-MRx code

C Petesch – Ch Primault
RCC-MRx sub-committee

1) *Presentation of RCC-MRx*

2) *RCC-MRx and welding*

3) *Welding qualification*

4) *Gen IV qualifications specificities*

5) *Conclusion*

RCC-CW
CIVIL WORKS

RCC-M
MECHANICAL COMPONENTS

RCC-E
ELECTRICAL AND I&C SYSTEMS

RCC-F
FIRE PROTECTION

RCC-C
FUEL ASSEMBLIES

RSE-M
IN-SERVICE INSPECTION RULES

RCC-MRx
MECHANICAL COMPONENTS

1) *Presentation of RCC-MRx*

2) *RCC-MRx and welding*

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Design & Construction Rules for Mechanical Components of High-Temperature, Experimental and Fusion Nuclear Installations

SECTION I RDG

- General provisions
- Entrance Keys – Applicable sets of rules
- Equipment specification
- Management system

SECTION II REC

- Additional requirements for using European standards**
NF EN 13445 NF EN 13480 Eurocode 3
- Special instructions for equipment subject to regulations**
French regulation ESP/ESPN
European regulation REACH

RCC-MRx
MECHANICAL
COMPONENTS

Design

Materials &
Examination
Methods

Welding &
Manufacturing
Operations

RCC-MRx
Règles de Conception et de Construction des Matériaux
Mécaniques des Installations Nucléaires
afcen

SECTION III Rules for nuclear installation mechanical components

VOLUME I: Design & Construction rules

- Volume A (RA): General provisions
- Volume B (RB): Class N1_{Rx} components & supports
- Volume C (RC): Class N2_{Rx} components & supports
- Volume D (RD): Class N3_{Rx} components & supports
- Volume K (RK): Examination, handling or drive mechanisms
- Volume L (RL): Irradiation devices
- Volume Z (Ai): Technical Appendices

VOLUME II
Materials

VOLUME III
Examination
Methods

VOLUME IV
Welding

VOLUME V
Manufacturing
operations

VOLUME VI
Probationary
Phase Rules

Last edition available
RCC-MRx 2018 !

Indian PFBR
RCC-MR 2002 edition

RCC-MR

1985 -1993 – 2002 – 2007

ITER Vacuum Vessel
RCC-MR 2007 edition

RCC-MRx

Règles de Conception et de Construction des Matériels
Mécaniques des Installations Nucléaires

afcen

2012 – 2015 – 2018 (->2022)

Règles de Conception et de Construction des Matériels
Mécaniques des Installations Nucléaires

afcen

MYRRHA
Primary
Cooling
system

ASTRID

European Spallation Source
target

RCC-MX

2005 – 2008

**Reactor
Building-Core**

**Nuclear Auxiliary
Building**

**Aseismic
bearing pads**

Jules Horowitz Reactor

RCC-MRx: DESIGN & CONSTRUCTION RULES FOR MECHANICAL COMPONENTS OF NUCLEAR INSTALLATIONS: HIGH TEMPERATURE, RESEARCH AND FUSION REACTORS

VOLUME I
Design

VOLUME II
Materials

VOLUME III
Examination
Methods

VOLUME IV
Welding

VOLUME V
Manufacturing
operations

RCC-CW
CIVIL WORKS

RCC-M
MECHANICAL COMPONENTS

RCC-E
ELECTRICAL AND I&C SYSTEMS

RCC-F
FIRE PROTECTION

RCC-C
FUEL ASSEMBLIES

RSE-M
IN-SERVICE INSPECTION RULES

RCC-MRx
MECHANICAL COMPONENTS

1) *Presentation of RCC-MRx*

2) *RCC-MRx and welding*

3) *Welding qualification*

4) *Gen IV qualifications specificities*

5) *Conclusion*

Welding?

- Manufacturing sequence to join parts of a component:
 - Generally with heating (sometimes pressure or combined)
 - With filler material (or not)

Why a special attention to welding ?

- The welding operation induces local modifications of the metal:
 - Residual stresses
 - Technological defects
 - Modified mechanical properties...
- « equivalence » of the welded part to base metal to be demonstrated :
 - for design values (S_m , S , ...)
 - Welds should not be the "weak areas" of the component
- Difficulty: After welding, there is no technical way to determine the true properties of a weldment (if you don't want to destroy it!)

Welding is everywhere...

But you have a « welding obstacle course »

Tome 1
Subsection A

- Which component? (RB,RC,RD, RK,RL, RE,RG,RI)
- Which code level? (N1,N2,N3)

Tome 1
Subsection RB (RC..)

- Allowable welds
- Consideration of welds in design (weld factors,..)

Tome 4
Welding

- **Qualification and welding**

REQUIREMENTS BEFORE WELDING

- *RS 1300 Weldability* of materials
- *RS 6000* Technical qualification of production **workshop**
- *RS 5000* Qualification of **filler materials** when trade designation qualification is required and in any case *RS 2000 acceptance testing of filler materials*
- *RS 3000* Qualification of the **Welding procedure**
- *RS 4000* qualification of **welders**

WELDING

RS 7000 Production welds

- *RS 7200 Storage* and use of the welding materials
- *RS 7300 Preparation* and examination **of edges and surfaces** for welding
- *RS 7400 Execution* of production welds
- *RS 7500* Weld related **heat treatments**
- *RS 7600 Repair* by welding
- *RS 7700 Non-destructive examination* of production welds
- *RS 7800 Destructive testing* of production welds - production weld test coupons

RS 9000

Destructive tests and examinations on welds

RS 10000

welding coordination

1) *Presentation of RCC-MRx*

2) *RCC-MRx and welding*

3) *Welding qualification*

4) *Gen IV qualifications specificities*

5) *Conclusion*

Prior
welding

- Scope: to demonstrate the weldability of the material (BM)
- ***The Material Weldability Report*** is based on experience feedback and welding procedure qualification. It includes for the weldment at the final stage (HAZ + WM and if necessary after thermal treatment) :
 - Metallurgical characteristics,
 - Mechanical properties,
 - Resistance to various type of cracking during/after welding,
 - Resistance to lamellar tearing (when risk exists),
 - Service performance.
- Usually, the Material Weldability Report is included in the Material File (RB,RC,RD 2000)

Prior
welding

- Scope : Evaluate the capacity and technical resources of the workshop for carrying out welding operations.
- Qualification bases
 - Installation
 - Welding equipment
 - Heat treatment facilities
 - Destructive and ND examination facilities
 - Personnel and supervision
 - Experience
- Qualification report
 - General case : issued by the manufacturer
 - Particular welding operation : demonstration that the level of skill has been maintained (checked every 2 years) --> ex : tube to tube plate welds

Prior
welding

- RS 5000 covers filler materials for which a trade designation qualification is required
- As a general rule, qualification is first required for all products associated with flux
 - Powdered fluxes (associated with wire or strip electrode of given chemical composition),
 - Flux-cored wires,
 - Covered electrodes.
- Qualification requirement is also extended to any filler material likely to operate at temperatures higher than 375°C
- Documents included in the qualification report
 - **Qualification Data Sheet** prepared by the Supplier (shall assume the repeatability of the production) ---> results of the tests carried out on several lots of the filler material and on deposited metal on a plate (outside the dilution zone) ; document with recommendations for storage and drying conditions,
 - Qualification Certificate reporting tests performed by the Manufacturer ----> tests on products, deposited metal and standard test piece or based on a **Welding Procedure Qualification Report** (as per RS 3000).

Prior
welding

- Scope : Define the acceptance criteria of the filler material to be used for welding
- The main purpose is to verify that the lots of filler materials used in production have the same quality/requirements than those who have undergone qualification tests (filler material and welding procedure qualification)
- Tests are realized :
 - on products (solid wires and strips)
 - on deposit weld metal (tests shall be carried out under reproducible conditions : outside dilution zone), with or/and without simulated production heat treatment
 - Acceptance criteria can be found in **Reference Data Sheets**

Tests to be done depend on the final use of the filler materials (resistant weld, cladding, ...)

- Associated documentation: Acceptance Specification (drawn by the Manufacturer)

Prior welding

Reference data sheets are given for filler materials recognized for use within the scope of RCC-MRx (return of experience)

- Acceptance tests to be performed and criteria
- Base metals to be welded with
- Range of application
- There are two kinds of reference data sheets
 - For current use (up to 375°C) : non alloyed or alloyed steels (RS 2800) ; stainless steels or nickel base alloys (RS 2900)
 - For specific use
 - Research reactors : aluminium and zirconium alloys (RS 2600)
 - High temperature use : stainless steels for temperatures above 375°C (Gen IV)

DESIGNATION: E19 9 L (E 308 L)		PROCESS: Manual Arc										
STANDARD: EN 1600 (AWS A5.4)		TYPE OF PRODUCT: Covered electrode										
GRADE: Austenitic-ferritic stainless steel												
1. CHEMICAL ANALYSIS												
(%)	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Ni	Cr	Mo	Co	Cu	V	Fe
In welding material												
In deposited metal	≤ 0.035	≤ 0.90	≤ 2.50**	≤ 0.025	≤ 0.025	9.00 - 12.00	18.00 - 21.00	≤ 0.50	≤ 0.20			
2. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES												
a. Tensile test												
Weld condition	Tensile test at room temperature				Tensile test at °C 35							
	R _{p0.2}	R _m	A	Z	R _{p0.2}	R _m	A					
As welded	≥ 210 MPa	≥ 520 MPa - ≤ 670 MPa	≥ 30 %		≥ 125 MPa							
b. Charpy impact test												
Weld condition	KV at room temp.		KV at 0 °C		KV at - 20 °C							
	average (4)	indiv. (4)	average (4)	average (4)	indiv. (4)	average (4)						
As welded	≥ 60 J	≥ 42 J										
3. BASE METAL - TYPE OF WELD												
										1 = Strength welds and		
										2 = TIG root pass and s		
										3 = Cladding		
Base metal								Weld				
								1	2	3		
X2CrNi18-9, X2CrNi19-11								(1)	X		X	
X2CrNi19-10 with controlled nitrogen content								(1)	X		X	
RM 341-1 (low ferrite GX3CrNi19-9)								(1)	X		X	
4. COMMENTS and NOTES												
* Preferred max value 12%, evaluated using Delong diagram (RMC 1361.3)												
** For cladding, the Mn content is more limited pour les revêtements, on limitera la teneur en Mn (RS for inf.: measurement for information purposes.												
(1) May be used for components operating permanently at temperatures less than 375°C.												
(4) Average (average) or individual (indiv.) value of the energy KV absorbed by breakage on 3 Charpy												

Prior
welding

RS 3000 contains the conditions for the execution of Qualification tests and the area of validity of an approved Welding Procedure

- The preparation, execution and examination of the Qualification Test piece is dependant from :
 - The welding process (TIG, MIG, laser beam, ...)
 - The base metal and filler material
 - The type of weld deposit (cladding, strength weld, ...)
 - The type of joint (butt weld, fillet weld, ...)
- Rules for arc welding are mainly based on EN ISO standards amended with specific RCC-MRx requirements
- Rules for other welding processes (laser beam, electron beam, diffusion welding, friction welding) are directly defined by RCC-MRx

In the same way, RS 4000 gives the conditions to qualify welders and operators and the associated area of validity

- Rules are generally based on EN ISO standards for welders/operators' qualification with additional requirements

1) *Presentation of RCC-MRx*

2) *RCC-MRx and welding*

3) *Welding qualification*

4) **Gen IV reactors qualifications specificities**

5) *Conclusion*

Today: Sodium/high temperatures fully implemented

- Service conditions
 - Long term High Temperature (HT) means $> 375^{\circ}\text{C}$ for steels and nickel alloys. Creep resistance and thermal ageing are to be taken into account
 - In some cases : exposed to liquid sodium (corrosion resistance)
- Materials for HT applications
 - Stainless steel (SS) grades
 - Nitrogen controlled X2CrNiMo17-12 [some kind of 316L(N)] : the most used grade for the reactor and associated circuits
 - Specific X2CrNiMo17-12 (some kind of 316L) : for high temperature / low stress conditions (piping)
 - Nitrogen controlled X2CrNi19-10 [some kind of 304L(N)] not really used (X2CrNiMo17-12 preferred)
 - X2CrNi18-10 [some kind of 304L] : mainly for cold sodium piping
 - GX3CrNi20-09 (cast low ferrite 304L)
 - Ferritic steels
 - 10CrMo9.10 à 2,25 % or 13CrMo4.4
 - Modified 9Cr1Mo
 - Others
 - Alloy 800 SPX

- Balance is to be found in the chemical composition of high temperature products to manage
 - Weldability,
 - Thermal ageing,
 - Creep rupture damage,
 - Corrosion resistance (for those required for)
- Proofs are to be given that the filler materials and welding procedures will lead to safe welds
- Specific considerations for weldability of austenitic stainless steels
 - These products generally require 5 to 15% of ferrite to avoid hot cracking susceptibility ; for Gen IV use, ferrite content as to be lowered to avoid induced fragility due to thermal ageing

- Any filler material likely to operate at temperatures above 375°C has to be qualified as per RS 5000 (not only those used with flux)
- For those products
 - The basic requirements for qualification (tests on product, tests on weld deposit on plate, tests on a test piece) are to be performed,
 - These basic requirements are completed to some specific ones to validate their use regarding :
 - Weldability issue (austenitic SS),
 - Long term high temperature conditions
 - Filler materials for cladding and some specific type of deposits are exempted from these complementary requirements.
 - Requirements depends on the grades of materials (non alloyed or low alloyed steels, stainless steels, nickel alloys)

- RS 5300 filler material qualification tests for non-alloyed and low alloyed steels
 - Complementary for weld metal on plate flat position

RS 5312.2 Case of components likely to operate at temperatures higher than 375°C

- a. The flux-wire combinations used for submerged arc welding (121) in two passes or less are not subject to the complementary provisions of the present section and follow the general case.
- b. The tests on weld metal outside the dilution zone (test plates) shall be carried out in compliance with the provisions of **RS 2000**.
- c. The weld metal deposited by filler materials used for welding Cr-Mo or Cr-Mo-V steel components (except 0.5% Cr – 0.5% Mo steel with a thickness less than 12 mm) shall be qualified for the Reference Heat Treatment.
- d. The tests on weld metal outside the dilution zone include:
 - For at least 5 lots, the tests defined in **RS 5312.1**,
 - For at least 3 lots, the short duration creep tests in the conditions prescribed by the Reference Data Sheets according to **RS 2700** or by the particular Data Sheet defined in **RS 2542**, and following the requirements of **RS 9700**,
 - For at least 2 lots, if the operating temperature of the components is higher than 450°C, the long duration creep tests in the conditions prescribed by the Reference Data Sheets according to **RS 2700** or by the particular Data Sheet defined in **RS 2542**, and following the requirements of **RS 9700**.

However, for 2.5 mm dia. electrodes used only for root welding, non-performance of long duration creep tests is allowed.

- Complementary to tests on test piece

RS 5313.2 Case of components likely to operate at temperatures higher than 375°C

The flux-wire combinations used for submerged arc welding (121) in two passes or less are not subject to the complementary provisions of the present section and follow the general case.

The test pieces used for the qualification of filler materials used for welding Cr-Mo or Cr-Mo-V steel components (except 0.5% Cr – 0.5% Mo steel with a thickness less than 12 mm) shall be qualified for the Reference Heat Treatment.

The provisions of the general case are completed by the following tests:

- a. The transverse tensile test at high temperature in the conditions prescribed by the Reference Data Sheets (**RS 2700**) or by the particular Data Sheet defined in **RS 2542**, and following the requirements of **RS 9100**.
- b. If the operating temperature of the component is higher than 450°C, or for the filler materials that are not referenced in the **RS 2700** Reference Data Sheets (whatever the operating temperature above 375°C), the long duration creep tests following the requirements of **RS 9700**. These tests are performed using test specimens transversally sampled on a test piece welded in flat position (PA) and, for the extension of the utilization range to other positions, on a test piece welded in vertical-up position (PF).

- RS 5400 filler material qualification tests for austenitic stainless steels and austenitic-ferritic stainless steels
 - Complementary for weld metal on plate flat position

RS 5412.2 *Case of components likely to operate at temperatures higher than 375°C*

- a. The flux-wire combinations used for submerged arc welding (121) in two passes or less are not subject to the complementary provisions of the present section and follow the general case.
- b. The tests on weld metal outside the dilution zone (test plates) shall be carried out in compliance with the provisions of **RS 2000**.
- c. The tests on weld metal outside the dilution zone include:
 - For at least 5 lots, the tests defined in **RS 5412.1**,
 - For at least 3 lots, if the operating temperature of the components is higher than 425°C, the short duration creep tests in the conditions prescribed by the Reference Data Sheets (**RS 2700**) or by the particular Data Sheet defined in **RS 2542**, and following the requirements of **RS 9700**,
 - For at least 3 lots, Charpy V-notch impact tests after Accelerated Ageing Heat Treatment in the conditions prescribed by the Reference Data Sheets (**RS 2700**) or by the particular Data Sheet defined in **RS 2542**, and following the requirements of **RS 9800**,
 - For at least 2 lots, if the operating temperature of the components is higher than 500°C, the long duration creep tests in the conditions prescribed by the Reference Data Sheets (**RS 2700**) or by the particular Data Sheet defined in **RS 2542**, and following the requirements of **RS 9700**.However, for 2.5 mm dia. electrodes used only for root welding, non-performance of long duration creep tests is allowed.

- Complementary to tests on test piece

RS 5413.2 *Case of components likely to operate at temperatures higher than 375°C*

The flux-wire combinations used for submerged arc welding (121) in two passes or less are not subject to the complementary provisions of the present section and follow the general case.

The provisions of the general case are amended and completed by the following tests:

- a. The transverse tensile test at high temperature in the conditions prescribed by the Reference Data Sheets (**RS 2700**) or by the particular Data Sheet defined in **RS 2542**, and following the requirements of **RS 9100**.
- b. The determination of the delta ferrite content: the evaluation made using the non-modified Schaeffler diagram (**Fig. RMC 1361.1**) shall lie between 3% and 7%. In case of doubt, an additional test may be performed by a magnetic saturation method or direct magnetic measurement (the apparatus having been calibrated beforehand); the results obtained shall then lie between 2% and 7%.
- c. If the operating temperature of the component is higher than 500°C, or for the filler materials that are not referenced in the **RS 2700** Reference Data Sheets (whatever the operating temperature above 375°C), the long duration creep tests following the requirements of **RS 9700**. These tests are performed using test specimens transversally sampled on a test piece welded in flat position (PA) and, for the extension of the utilization range to other positions, on a test piece welded in vertical-up position (PF).

- RS 5600 filler material qualification tests for nickel alloy strength welds
- Complementary for weld metal on plate flat position

RS 5612.2 Case of components likely to operate at temperatures higher than 375°C

- a. The flux-wire combinations used for submerged arc welding (121) in two passes or less are not subject to the complementary provisions of the present section and follow the general case.
- b. The tests on weld metal outside the dilution zone (test plates) shall be carried out in compliance with the provisions of **RS 2000**.
- c. The tests on weld metal outside the dilution zone include:
 - For at least 5 lots, the tests defined in **RS 5612.1**,
 - For at least 3 lots, if the operating temperature of the components is higher than 425°C, the short duration creep tests in the conditions prescribed by the Reference Data Sheets (**RS 2700**) or by the particular Data Sheet defined in **RS 2542**, and following the requirements of **RS 9700**,
 - For at least 2 lots, if the operating temperature of the components is higher than 500°C, the long duration creep tests in the conditions prescribed by the Reference Data Sheets (**RS 2700**) or by the particular Data Sheet defined in **RS 2542**, and following the requirements of **RS 9700**,
However, for 2.5 mm dia. electrodes used only for root welding, non-performance of long duration creep tests is allowed.

- Complementary to tests on test piece

RS 5613.2 Case of components likely to operate at temperatures higher than 375°C

The flux-wire combinations used for submerged arc welding (121) in two passes or less are not subject to the complementary provisions of the present section and follow the general case.

The provisions of the general case are completed by the following tests:

- a. The transverse tensile test at high temperature in the conditions prescribed by the Reference Data Sheets (**RS 2700**) or by the particular Data Sheet defined in **RS 2542**, and following the requirements of **RS 9100**.
- b. If the operating temperature of the component is higher than 500°C, or for the filler materials that are not referenced in the **RS 2700** Reference Data Sheets (whatever the operating temperature above 375°C), the long duration creep tests following the requirements of **RS 9700**. These tests are performed using test specimens transversely sampled on a test piece welded in flat position (PA) and, for the extension of the utilization range to other positions, on a test piece welded in vertical-up position (PF).

- For stainless steels, only those covered by a RS 2700 Reference Data Sheets are accepted for use > 375°C

RS 2700 REFERENCE DATA SHEETS OF FILLER MATERIALS – STAINLESS STEEL USED AT HIGH TEMPERATURE

The Reference Data Sheets included in **RS 2700** specify the results of chemical analyses and the mechanical properties to be obtained for each type of filler material - in as welded condition or after heat treatment if applicable.

These Reference Data Sheets are listed as follows

- **RS 2711.1** Reference Data Sheet - 19Cr12Ni2Mo stainless steel covered electrode
- **RS 2711.2** Reference Data Sheet - 16Cr8Ni2Mo stainless steel covered electrode
- **RS 2712.2** Reference Data Sheet - 16Cr8Ni2Mo stainless steel wire for TIG welding
- **RS 2712.4** Reference Data Sheet - Z15CNW22-12 grade steel wire for TIG welding
- **RS 2713.1** Reference Data Sheet - 19Cr12Ni2Mo stainless steel wire/flux couple for submerged arc welding
- **RS 2713.2** Reference Data Sheet - 16Cr8Ni2Mo stainless steel wire/flux couple for submerged arc welding

- Specificity of RS 2700 filler materials
 - All filler materials are very low ferrite content : $\leq 7\%$ and even less (compared to 5 to 15% generally required)
 - Supplementary tests compared to RS 2900 :
 - Additional test pieces required (type as per RS 5000 i.e on qualification test piece, taking into account welding position)
 - Hot temperature tests
 - Hot cracking tests
 - Creep resistance tests

- Reference data sheets include much more requirements (than RS 2900), based on several test pieces

Filler material	Designation	Process	Reference Data Sheet									
Covered electrode	19Cr12Ni2Mo (Non standard)	Manual arc 111	RS 2711.1									
1. Tests on test plate made in flat position												
1.1 Chemical analysis												
(%)	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Ni	Mo	N (1)	Cu	O (1)	Co
Min	0.045	0.40	1.2			18.0	11.0	1.9				
Max	0.055	0.70	1.8	0.025	0.020	19.0	12.0	2.2		0.30		0.20
1.2 Ferrite content												
	Schaeffer diagram reading (Fig. RMC 1361.1)			Magnetic method (RMC 1362.2)								
Min	3 %			3 %								
Max	7 %			7 %								
1.3 Mechanical tests												
1.3.1 Tensile test (longitudinal) (RS 2536)												
Temperature	Room			200°C (3)			550°C (3)					
	R _{0.2}	R _m	A	R _{0.2}	R _m	A	R _{0.2}	R _m	A			
Flat position test plate	≥ 350 MPa	≥ 550 MPa	≥ 35 %	(1)	≥ 425 MPa	(1)	(1)	≥ 380 MPa	≥ 20%			
1.3.2 Charpy impact tests (RS 2536)												
Temperature	Room											
	KV (2)											
Flat position test plate	≥ 60 J											
1.3.3 Charpy impact tests after Accelerated Aging Heat Treatment (RS 9900)												
Temperature	Room			Accelerated Aging Heat Treatment: Temperature = 750 °C - Duration = 100 h								
	KV (2)											
Flat position test plate	≥ 25 J											
1.4 Groove cracking test (RS 9920)												
1.5 Accelerated intergranular corrosion test (RS 9600)												
1.6 Creep tests (RS 9720)												
Temperature	Stress	Time to rupture										
550°C	260 Mpa	≥ 700 h										
550°C	230 Mpa	≥ 2000 h										
2. Tests on joint made in vertical-up position (RS 2536.5b and RS 9940)												
2.1 Chemical analysis: as in 1.1 for information purposes												
2.2 Ferrite content: magnetic method (RMC 1362.2) ≥ 2 %												
2.3 Crack tests (RS 9940)												
3. Tests on Qualification Test piece (RS 3230 and RS 3900)												
3.1 Qualification in "flat position" PA												
3.1.1 Chemical analysis: as in 1.1 for information purposes												
3.1.2 Ferrite content: magnetic method (RMC 1362.2) - for information purposes												
3.1.3 Tensile test (longitudinal) at room temperature (RS 3234.61)												
Temperature	Room											
	R _{0.2}	R _m	A									
	≥ 350 MPa	≥ 550 MPa	≥ 35 %									

Additional for HT use

Filler material	Designation	Process	Reference Data Sheet		
Covered electrode	19Cr12Ni2Mo (Non standard)	Manual arc 111	RS 2711.1		
3.1.4 Tensile test (transversal) (RS 3234)					
Base metal	Weld condition	Room	200°C (3)	450°C (3)	550°C (3)
		R _m	R _m	R _m	R _m
X2CrNiMo17-12-2 with controlled nitrogen content	As welded	≥ 525 MPa	≥ 425 MPa		≥ 380 MPa
X2CrNiMo17-12-2 with controlled nitrogen content	DSHT (See §5 hereunder)	≥ 525 MPa			≥ 340 MPa
X2CrNiMo17-12-2, X2CrNiMo17-12-3 and X2CrNiMo18-14-3	As welded	≥ 520 MPa			≥ 350 MPa
X2CrNi19-10 with controlled nitrogen content	As welded	≥ 510 MPa			≥ 390 MPa
X2CrNi19-11	As welded	≥ 500 MPa			≥ 345 MPa
3.1.5 Charpy impact tests					
Weld condition	Temperature	Room			
		KV (2)			
As welded		≥ 60 J			
DSHT (See §5 hereunder)		≥ 50 J			
3.1.6 Bend tests (RS 3234.2)					
3.1.7 Accelerated intergranular corrosion test (RS 9600)					
3.2 Qualification in other position than "flat position"					
3.2.1 Chemical analysis: as in 1.1 for information purposes					
3.2.2 Ferrite content: magnetic method (RMC 1362.2) - for information purposes					
3.2.3 Tensile test (longitudinal) at room temperature (RS 3234.61)					
Temperature	Room				
	R _{0.2}	R _m	A		
	≥ 350 MPa	≥ 550 MPa	≥ 30 %		
3.2.4 Tensile test (transversal): see 3.1.4					
3.2.5 Charpy impact tests at room temperature: see 3.1.5					
3.2.6 Bend tests (RS 3234.2)					
3.2.7 Accelerated intergranular corrosion test (RS 9600)					
4. Base metal and properties of welded joints					
Grades which can be joined using the filler material in question:					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> X2CrNiMo17-12-2 with controlled nitrogen content, X2CrNi19-10 with controlled nitrogen content, X2CrNi19-11, X2CrNiMo17-12-2, X2CrNiMo17-12-3 and X2CrNiMo18-4-3 					
All the properties of welded joints to be used are defined in appendix A9 (A9.GEN).					
5. Range of application					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Positions: flat position - extension to the other positions with supplementary acceptance tests on vertical-up welds. procedures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> As welded: procedure without heat treatment. DSHT: procedure with Dimensional Stability Heat Treatment of 50 h at 650 °C. The particular required values are given in 3.1.4 and 3.1.5. Operating temperature ≤ 550°C. 					
Notes:					
(1) Measurement for information purposes.					
(2) Individual value of the energy KV absorbed by breakage on Charpy V-notch test specimens.					
(3) Temperature chosen according the specified use.					

- Chemical composition : Ranges more stringent for almost all elements
- Ferrite content : Schaeffler diagram generally required (rather than Delong : RS 2900) ; A complementary requirement for magnetic saturation method on weld deposit

Filler material	Designation	Process	Reference Data Sheet RS 2711.1									
Covered electrode	19Cr12Ni2Mo (Non standard)	Manual arc 111										
1. Tests on test plate made in flat position												
1.1 Chemical analysis												
(%)	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Ni	Mo	N (t)	Cu	O (t)	Co
Min	0.045	0.40	1.2			18.0	11.0	1.9				
Max	0.055	0.70	1.8	0.025	0.020	19.0	12.0	2.2		0.30		0.20
1.2 Ferrite content												
	Schaeffler diagram reading (Fig. RMC 1361.1)		Magnetic method (RMC 1362.2)									
Min	3 %		3 %									
Max	7 %		7 %									

DESIGNATION:	E 19 12 3 L (E 316 L)	PROCESS:	Arc manual	Reference Data Sheet RS 2925											
STANDARD:	EN 1600 (AWS A5.4)	TYPE OF PRODUCT:	Covered electrodes												
GRADE:	Austenitic-ferritic stainless steel														
1. CHEMICAL ANALYSIS															
(%)	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Ni	Cr	Mo	Co	Cu	V	Fe	N ₂	Ta + Nb	calculated δ ferrite
In welding material															
In deposited metal	≤ 0.035	≤ 0.90	≤ 2.50	≤ 0.025	≤ 0.025	12.00 – 14.00	18.00 – 20.00	2.00 – 3.00	≤ 0.20				for inf.		* 5 - 15

- Additional mechanical testing at room and 500°C

1.3 Mechanical tests									
1.3.1 Tensile test (longitudinal) (RS 2536)									
Temperature	Room			200°C (3)			550°C (3)		
	R _{p0.2}	R _m	A	R _{p0.2}	R _m	A	R _{p0.2}	R _m	A
Flat position test plate	≥ 350 MPa	≥ 550 MPa	≥ 35 %	(1)	≥ 425 MPa	(1)	(1)	≥ 380 MPa	≥ 20%

- Additional Charpy impact tests after ageing heat treatment mandatory

1.3.2 Charpy impact tests (RS 2536)		
Temperature	Room	
	KV (2)	
Flat position test plate	≥ 60 J	
1.3.3 Charpy impact tests after Accelerated Aging HeatTreatment (RS 9800)		
Temperature	Room	Accelerated Aging HeatTreatment: Temperature = 750 °C - Duration = 100 h
	KV (2)	
Flat position test plate	≥ 25 J	

- Corrosion test and creep tests are

1.6 Creep tests (RS 9720)		
Temperature	Stress	Time to rupture
550°C	260 Mpa	≥ 700 h
550°C	230 Mpa	≥ 2000 h

- Crack susceptibility test is/are required (ferrite content is lower than 5%)
 - Groove cracking test for all filler RS 2700 materials : RS 9920 for covered electrodes and RS 9930 for solid rods and electrodes

Figure RS 9920: crack-ability tests - groove deposit for electrodes depositing a high alloy steel or an austenitic alloy

Figure RS 9930: linear groove cracking test for filler wires - test joints

- cracking test in vertical-up assembly (RS 9940) for covered electrodes only

- Qualification test piece on flat position required

- Classic tests (tensile, Charpy, bend test, chemical composition, ferrite content) are to be performed at standard temperature ; results mandatory or for information

3. Tests on Qualification Test piece (RS 3230 and RS 3900)

3.1 Qualification in "flat position PA"

3.1.1 Chemical analysis: as in 1.1 for information purposes			
3.1.2 Ferrite content: magnetic method (RMC 1362.2) - for information purposes			
3.1.3 Tensile test (longitudinal) at room temperature (RS 3234.61)			
Temperature	Room		
	R _{0.2}	R _m	A
	≥ 350 MPa	≥ 550 MPa	≥ 35 %

3.1.5 Charpy impact tests		
Temperature	Room	
Weld condition	KV (2)	
As welded	≥ 60 J	
DSHT (See §5 hereunder)	≥ 50 J	
3.1.6 Bend tests (RS 3234.2)		
3.1.7 Accelerated intergranular corrosion test (RS 9600)		

- Additional tests at higher temperature with requirements depending on the base material

3.1.4 Tensile test (transversal) (RS 3234)					
Base metal	Weld condition	Room	200°C (3)	450°C (3)	550°C (3)
		R _m	R _m	R _m	R _m
X2CrNiMo17-12-2 with controlled nitrogen content	As welded	≥ 525 MPa	≥ 425 MPa		≥ 380 MPa
X2CrNiMo17-12-2 with controlled nitrogen content	DSHT (See §5 hereunder)	≥ 525 MPa			≥ 340 MPa
X2CrNiMo17-12-2, X2CrNiMo17-12-3 and X2CrNiMo18-14-3	As welded	≥ 520 MPa			≥ 350 MPa
X2CrNi19-10 with controlled nitrogen content	As welded	≥ 510 MPa		≥ 390 MPa	
X2CrNi19-11	As welded	≥ 500 MPa		≥ 345 MPa	

- When a Dimensional Stability Heat Treatment (DSHT) is to be used during manufacturing, some tests are to be performed in both conditions (with or without DSHT)

- Gives requirements :
 - To extend some WPQ for welds operating at “high” temperatures (including laser beam and electron beam welding) :
 - 375 °C for non-austenitic steels,
 - 425°C for austenitic stainless steels and nickel alloys
 - To be called of RS 5000 filler material qualification,
- Aim to verify:
 - high temperature tensile test properties
 - behaviour of the welded assembly in the creep range (accelerated tests)
 - structural stability (level of KV after thermal ageing)
 - internal soundness of the weld (+HAZ) through metallographic tests
- How?
 - In addition of RS 3200, RS 3300, RS 3560 or RS 3570
 - Test on test-plate buttering (Characterisation of the filler materials in creep domain - RS 3940)
 - Crack test (reference to RS 5000)
 - Test on welded assemblies (creep test – RS 3930)
 - Use of a high temperature filler material according to RS 2700 : the tests to be conducted and the expected results are given in the data sheet

- No specific requirements for these qualifications in relation to welds operating at "high temperature"

RCC-CW
CIVIL WORKS

RCC-M
MECHANICAL COMPONENTS

RCC-E
ELECTRICAL AND I&C SYSTEMS

RCC-F
FIRE PROTECTION

RCC-C
FUEL ASSEMBLIES

RSE-M
IN-SERVICE INSPECTION RULES

RCC-MRx
MECHANICAL COMPONENTS

1) *Presentation of RCC-MRx*

2) *RCC-MRx and welding*

3) *Welding qualification*

4) *Gen IV qualifications specificities*

5) *Conclusion*

Base metal: grade	Base metal: Reference Procurement Specification or standard	Base metal: Properties Group	Filler metal: grade Reference Data Sheet	Process	Welding procedure: qualification	Jm	Jf	Welded joint: Properties Group
5754 - O	RM 512-1, RM 512-2 RM 513-1, RM 515-1	A3.1A	EN AW 5356 RS 2621	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3300	1	later	Not supplied
			EN AW 5356	Inert gas (MIG)	RS 3300	1	later	Not supplied
			EN AW 5754 RS 2631	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3300	1	later	Not supplied
			EN AW 5754	Inert gas (MIG)	RS 3300	1	later	Not supplied
			EN AW 5183 RS 2651	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3300	1	later	Not supplied
			EN AW 5183	Inert gas (MIG)	RS 3300	1	later	Not supplied
6061 – T6	RM 522-2, RM 522-3, RM 522-4 RM 523-1, RM 525-1	A3.2A	Without	Electron beam	RS 3560	1	later	-
			EN AW 4043 RS 2641	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3300	0.6	later	A9-J2A
			EN AW 4043	Inert gas (MIG)	RS 3300			A9-J2A
			EN AW 5356 RS 2621	Inert gas (TIG)	RS 3300			A9-J2A
			EN AW 5356	Inert gas (MIG)	RS 3300			A9-J2A
			4043	Electron beam	RS 3560			A9-J2A
			4047	Electron beam	RS 3560	later	later	A9-J2A
			Without	Electron beam	RS 3560	later	later	Not supplied
Zircaloy 2	RM 613-1, RM614-1	A3.1Z	Without	Electron beam	RS 3560	1	later	Not supplied
Zircaloy 4	RM 615-1	A3.2Z	Without	Electron beam	RS 3560	1	later	A9-J2Z

– For several materials :
welded joint are missing
with respect to :

- Fatigue behaviors
- Creep behaviors

Creep – Stainless Steel

Base metal: grade	Base metal: Reference Procurement Specification or standard	Base metal: Properties Group	Filler metal: grade Reference Data Sheet	Process	Welding procedure: qualification	Welded joint: Properties Group
X2CrNiMo17-12-2 (B)	RM 332-1, RM 332-3 RM 332-4, RM 333-1 RM 334-1, RM 334-2 RM 334-4, RM 334-6 RM 334-6, RM 334-7, RM 334-8	A3.1S	19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2711.1	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	A6-J1S
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2711.2	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	A6-J1S
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2712.1 (later)	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2712.2	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2713.1	Submerged arc	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2713.2	Submerged arc	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2711.1	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	A6-J3S
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2711.2	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	A6-J3S
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2712.1 (later)	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2712.2	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
X2CrNiMo17-12-2 X2CrNiMo17-12-3 X2CrNiMo18-14-3	RM 332-2, RM 332-5 RM 333-2, RM 333-3 RM 333-5 RM 334-1, RM 334-2 RM 334-5, RM 334-6 RM 334-7, RM 334-8 RM 335-2 EN 10108-7 EN 10222-5 EN 10272	A3.3S	19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2711.1	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	A6-J3S
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2711.2	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	A6-J3S
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2712.1 (later)	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2712.2	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2713.1	Submerged arc	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2713.2	Submerged arc	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2711.1	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2711.2	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2712.1 (later)	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2712.2	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
X5CrNiMo17-12-2	RM 332-2, RM 332-5 RM 333-2, RM 334-2 RM 334-5	Not supplied	19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2711.1 (later)	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2712.1 (later)	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2713.1	Submerged arc	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2713.2	Submerged arc	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2711.1	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2711.2	Covered electrode	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2712.1 (later)	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2712.2	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2713.1	Submerged arc	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			19Cr19Ni2Mo RS 2713.2	Submerged arc	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
6061 – T6	RM 522-1, RM 522-2 RM 523-1, RM 525-1	A3.2A	Not supplied	Inert gaz (TIG)	RS 3200 + RS 3900	Not supplied
			Without	Electron beam	RS 3560 + RS 3900	Not supplied
Zircaloy 2	RM 613-1, RM614-1, RM 615-1	A3.1Z	Without	Electron beam	RS 3560 + RS 3900	Not supplied
Zircaloy 4		A3.2Z	Without	Electron beam	RS 3560 + RS 3900	Not supplied

– The specified welded joint :
• Feedback of R&D work
associated to reactor building

- SFR : PX & SPX
- JHR

Design recommendations (integrated in RPP14 in the 2018 RCC-MRx edition):

« The operator (Prime Contractor) should follow the recommendations hereafter in order to insure structural integrity under operating conditions (mainly coolant chemistry):

- The chosen material, in the chemistry controlled coolant, has the same behavior as in air except for the depletion of the corrosion allowance,
- All failure modes inside or outside of the design Code shall be identified and addressed,
- Flaws, local corrosion and local thinning will be detected before defects become critical(*), assuming a limited corrosion speed,
- The requested coolant parameters (composition, pressure, temperature, circulation speed...) will be satisfied all over the systems,
- Failure of the chemistry control system that could cause high speed corrosion is detected and the grace time is sufficient to take corrective action.”

- ✓ CW 64: « Design and Construction Codes for Gen II to IV nuclear facilities”
PG 2 "*Mechanics GEN IV and innovative reactors*“ lead by K Nilsson, JRC
- Identification of gaps/needs regarding welding and welds consideration
- Proposals for R&D and code evolution:
 - ⇒ **CEN WORKSHOP AGREEMENT CWA 17377**
 - *PG2/RD-01: “Development of Design Rules and Characterisation of Material Behaviour in Heavy Liquid Metal (HLM) Environments”*
 - *PG2/RD-02: “Methodology for the design and life-assessment of components exposed to 60 years' service-life”*
 - *PG2/RD-03: “Irradiated Characteristic for Advanced Reactor in Upset and Safety State”*
 - *PG2/RD-04: “Optimal weld design of 316 type steels for enhanced creep-fatigue endurance”*

- **Clearly identified as a major point for components fabrication, needing specific attention**
- **A qualification process is included in all the design codes for mechanical components but can differ depending on the scope of the code**
- **In the nuclear field, obligation to bring the demonstration of the final (including end-of-life) properties of the materials (including welds)**
- **Existing methods have to be completed/improved to face the GEN IV reactors challenges**

Thank you *Any question?*

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High-temperature design of welded joint for Generation-IV in ASME

4. October. 2021

KAERI

Hyeong-Yeon Lee

Outline

- 1. Introduction**
- 2. Elevated Temperature Design(ETD) Rules of ASME (ASME-HB & CC-2843)**
- 3. Treatment of welded joints in ETD rules**
- 4. Applications of design rules to welded components & piping**
- 5. HITEP platform for reliable integrity evaluation of welded joints**
- 6. Summary**

1. Introduction

❖ ETD* Rules for Gen.IV Reactors & ITER

- RCC-MRx
- ASME BPVC Section III Division 5 Subsection HB ('ASME-HB')
- ASME BPVC CC 2843-2 ('ASME CC-2843')

❖ ETD of welded joint is crucial in structural integrity ;

- Location with geometrical & metallurgical discontinuity
- Potential for limited ductility of weld metal
- Majority ($\geq 70\%$) of cracks & defects occur at welded joint

⇒ Reliability of design for welded joints determines structural integrity of high-temperature pressure boundary components.

ASTRID

MYRRHA

ITER

PGSFR (Korea)

* ETD : Elevated Temperature Design

II

Elevated temperature design rules of ASME

❖ Generation IV

- SFR (ASTRID, PFBR, PGSFR, JSFR)
- LFR (MYRRHA)

❖ ITER

❖ Thermal Energy Storage System

Thermal Energy Storage System

Elevated Temperature Design (ETD) Rules

❖ Nuclear grade

- **RCC-MRx**
- **ASME BPVC Section III Division 5 Subsection HB Subpart B ('ASME-HB')**
- **ASME BPVC CC-N898 (Alloy 617)**
- **JSME D&C Code for Fast Reactors (Japan)**
- **KEPIC MNH (Korea)**

❖ Non-nuclear grade

- **Pressure Vessel : ASME CC-2843*** (to Section VIII Div.2), ASME VIII Div.1, Div.2
- **Piping : ASME B31.1 / B31.3 (Low & high temperature)**

* ASME CC-2843 : Class 2 components (non-nuclear grade)

ASME BPVC ETD Rules

- **ASME BPVC Section III Div.5 Subsection HB Subpart B ('ASME-HB')** : Class A Components
 - ✓ App. HBB-II included (Use of SA-533 & SA-508 for Limited ET* Service) (**CC N-499**, previously)
- **ASME Div.5 Sebsec.HC Subpart B** : Class B components, ET service (**CC N-253**, previously)
- **ASME Div.5 Sebsec.HG Subpart B** : Class SM core supports, ET service (**CC N-201**, previously)
- **ASME CC-N898, Alloy 617**

* ET : Elevated Temperature

2. Flow diagram of ASME-HB

❖ ETD rules for

- Pressure Vessel (HBB-3200)
- Piping : incomplete (HBB-3600)

- Materials**
- 304SS
 - 316SS
 - 2.25Cr-1Mo
 - Mod.9Cr-1Mo
 - Alloy 800H
 - Alloy 718(Bolt)

Appendix HBB-T
(Non-mandatory)

- High temp : ASME-HB
- Low temp : ASME-NB

Flow diagram of ASME CC-2843

Non-nuclear ; ASME CC to Section VIII Div.2
Class 2 components (e.g Thermal Energy Storage)

❖ ETD rules for

- Pressure Vessel (class 2)

Materials

- 304SS
- 316SS
- 2.25Cr-1Mo
- Mod.9Cr-1Mo
- Alloy 800H
- Alloy 718(Bolt)

- High temp : ASME CC-2843
- Low temp : ASME VIII Div.2

Flow diagram of RCC-MRx (RB-3200)

❖ ETD rules for

- [Pressure Vessel \(RB-3200\)](#)
- [Piping \(RB-3600\)](#)

Materials

- 304
- 304L
- 316L
- 316L(N)
- 2.25Cr-1Mo
- Mod.9Cr-1Mo
- Alloy 800
- ...

- High temp : RCC-MRx
- Low temp : RCC-MRx

Comparison of ETD rules (1/2)

1) ASME-HB (nuclear, Pressure Vessel)

Step 4. Calculate the equivalent strain range for each point in time as:

$$\Delta\epsilon_{equiv.i} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2(1+\nu^*)} \left[\begin{aligned} &(\Delta\epsilon_{xi} - \Delta\epsilon_{yi})^2 + (\Delta\epsilon_{yi} - \Delta\epsilon_{zi})^2 \\ &+ (\Delta\epsilon_{zi} - \Delta\epsilon_{xi})^2 \\ &+ \frac{3}{2}(\Delta\gamma_{xyi}^2 + \Delta\gamma_{yzi}^2 + \Delta\gamma_{zxi}^2) \end{aligned} \right]^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

where

$\nu^* = 0.5$ when using the rules of HBB-T-1420

$\nu^* = 0.3$ when using the rules of HBB-T-1430

Step 5. Define $\Delta\epsilon_{max}$ as the maximum value of the above calculated equivalent strain ranges, $\Delta\epsilon_{equiv.i}$.

- Isochronous curves

2) ASME CC-2843 (non-nuclear grade, PV)

7.2 CREEP FATIGUE PROCEDURE

7.2.1 Creep Procedure. The creep procedure is performed as follows:

Step 1. Determine the maximum equivalent strain range, $\Delta\epsilon_{max}$, from the equation

$$\Delta\epsilon_{max} = \frac{2S_{alt}}{E} \quad (26)$$

$$2S_{alt} = (P_L + P_b + Q) \text{ at a given point}$$

- Isochronous curves

3) RCC-MRx (nuclear, PV & Piping)

Amplification due to plasticity – Calculation of $(\overline{\Delta\epsilon})$

For each of the cycles under analysis, the range of the total $\overline{\Delta\sigma}_{tot} = \overline{\Delta(P+Q+F)}$ must be known. This range can be obtained concerned or by using the stress concentration factor.

The value of $\overline{\Delta\epsilon}$ is the sum of the four terms $\overline{\Delta\epsilon}_1, \overline{\Delta\epsilon}_2, \overline{\Delta\epsilon}_3, \overline{\Delta\epsilon}_4$

$$\overline{\Delta\epsilon} = \overline{\Delta\epsilon}_1 + \overline{\Delta\epsilon}_2 + \overline{\Delta\epsilon}_3 + \overline{\Delta\epsilon}_4$$

$$\overline{\Delta\epsilon}_1 = \frac{2}{3} (1+\nu) \left(\overline{\Delta\sigma}_{tot} / E \right)$$

- Creep law is used for determining creep strain

$$\epsilon_{cr} = C_1 t^{C_2} \sigma^{n_1}$$

Comparison of ETD rules (2/2)

❖ Creep-Fatigue Damage Envelope

$$\sum_{j=1}^P \left(\frac{n}{N_d} \right)_j + \sum_{k=1}^q \left(\frac{\Delta t}{T_d} \right)_k \leq D$$

➤ ASME-HB

➤ ASME CC-2843

➤ RCC-MRx

Code Case N-812 Gr.91 Alternative C-F Rule

❖ Procedures of CC N-812 applicable (Gr.91)

- Elastic Analysis of ASME-HB (T-1430)
- Isochronous Curves (T-1433(a) Step 5(2))

ASME-HB

Code Case N-812

Alternative C-F Damage Envelope for 9Cr-1Mo-V

Ref. T. Asayama

Heat resistant materials in design rules (nuclear grade)

□ RCC-MRx

- 316L(N)
- 316L
- 304
- 304L
- Alloy 800H
- Gr.91
- Eurofer

□ ASME-HB (& ASME CC 2843-2*)

- Type 304 SS
- Type 316 SS
- Alloy 800H
- 9Cr-1Mo-V
- 2.25Cr-1Mo
- Alloy 718 (Bolt)

□ ASME Code Case N-898

- Alloy 617 (950°C, 100,000h CRS)

* ASME CC-2843 : non-nuclear grade (design rules)

Isochronous Curve - ASME (1/2)

Table HBB-T-1820-1
Temperature and Time Limits for Alloys in Isochronous Stress-Strain Curves

Material	Maximum Temperature, °F (°C)	Maximum Temperature, °F (°C)	Maximum Time, hr
304 SS	800 (427)	1,500 (816)	300,000
316 SS	800 (427)	1,500 (816)	300,000
Alloy 800H	800 (427)	1,400 (760)	300,000
2 ¹ / ₄ Cr-1Mo	700 (371)	1,200 (649)	300,000
9Cr-1Mo-V	700 (371)	1,200 (649)	300,000

□ Concept of isochronous curve in ASME-HB

Isochronous Curve 316SS - 540°C

Isochronous Curve - ASME (2/2)

❖ 2019 Ed.

❖ 2021 Ed.

Significant revision
: Formula given for Isochronous curves

HBB-T-1835 9Cr-1Mo-V

(a) Elastic Strain

$$\epsilon_e = \frac{\sigma}{E}$$

(b) Plastic Strain

$$\epsilon_p = 0 \text{ for } \sigma \leq RP$$

$$= \frac{1}{100b} \left[\ln \left(\frac{RP - RU}{\sigma - RU} \right) \right]^2 \text{ for } RP < \sigma < RU$$

(c) Creep Strain

$$\epsilon_c = \frac{1}{100} \left[D \sigma e^{V_0 \sigma_e - Q_0 / (T + 273.15)} t^{1/3} + C \sigma^n e^{V \sigma_e - Q / (T + 273.15)} t \right]$$

- C = 2.25 × 10²²
- D = 847,000 for T < 482
- = 82,196(T - 482) + 847,000 for 482 ≤ T < 537
- = 5,450,000 for T ≥ 537
- Q = 77,280
- Q₀ = 25,330 for TT < 537
- = 23,260 for TT ≥ 537
- V = 0.038
- V₀ = 0.023
- n = 5.0

Treatment of welded joints in ETD rules

- ❖ ASME-HB
- ❖ ASME CC-2843
(RCC-MRx)

Rules for Weldment : ASME-HB

❖ Special strain requirements at welds (HBB-T-1710)

- Due to potential for limited ductility of weld metal fatigue life at ET*
- Potential for high strain concentration,
- **Additional analysis requirements shall be satisfied.**
 - **Inelastic strains accumulated in the weld shall not exceed 1/2 strain values of BM**
 - **Base material properties are used at the welded region (FE analysis)**
 - **The analysis for strains & C-F interactions at welds shall use **stress and strain concentration factors appropriate for the worst surface geometry****

* ET : Elevated Temperature

What to consider associated with weldments

❖ Factors to be considered due to Weld @ elevated temperature

- Thermal expansion
- Creep rate
- Creep ductility
- Inelastic strain
- Fatigue life

❖ When deposited WM is used as reinforcement of nozzle, the coefficients of **thermal expansion of the BM, WM and nozzle shall not differ by more than 15% of the lowest coefficient involved.**

Damage Evaluation for Welded Joints

❖ ASME-HB

1. Fatigue Damage

$$N_d(\text{HAZ}) = \frac{1}{2} N_d(\text{base})$$

2. Creep Damage

T_d determined from $S_r \times R$ (Weld SRF)

- Welded joint (HAZ) : defined as $\pm 3t$

FIG. I-14.6F 9Cr-1Mo-V – EXPECTED MINIMUM STRESS-TO-RUPTURE, ksi (MPa)

$$\sum_{j=1}^p \left(\frac{n}{N_d} \right)_j + \sum_{k=1}^q \left(\frac{\Delta t}{T_d} \right)_k \leq D$$

❖ RCC-MR

1. Fatigue Damage

$$\overline{\Delta \sigma}_{weld} = \text{FSRF} \times \overline{\Delta \sigma}_{base}$$

$$\varepsilon_t - N(\text{HAZ}) = \varepsilon_{to} - N(\text{base}) / J_f(\text{curve})$$

2. Creep Damage

T_d determined from $S_r \times J_r$

Weld Coeff. in RCC-MRx (A9)

J_m : weld properties coeff.

J_t : coef. of weld creep properties

J_f : coef. of weld fatigue characteristics

J_r : coef. of weld rupture properties

Weld materials in ASME-HB

Table HBB-I-14.1(b)
Permissible Weld Materials

Base Material	Spec. No.	Class
Types 304 SS and 316 SS	SFA-5.4	E 308, E 308L, E 316, E 316L, E 16-8-2
	SFA-5.9	ER 308, ER 308L, ER 316, ER 316L, ER 16-8-2
	SFA-5.22	E 308, E 308T, E 308LT, E 316T, E316LT-1 EXXXT-G (16-8-2 chemistry)
Ni-Fe-Cr (Alloy 800H)	SFA-5.11	ENiCrFe-2
	SFA-5.14	ERNiCr-3
2 ¹ / ₄ Cr-1Mo	SFA-5.5	E 90XX-B3 (>0.05% Carbon)
	SFA-5.23	EB 3, ECB 3
	SFA-5.28	E 90C-B3 (>0.05% Carbon), ER 90S-B3
	SFA-5.29	E 90T-B3 (>0.05% Carbon)
9Cr-1Mo-V	SFA-5.5	E90XX-B9
	SFA-5.23	EB9
	SFA-5.28	ER90S-B9

Weld Stress Rupture Factor(R^*) in ASME (creep damage relevant)

S_r (Min. stress-to-rupture stress) x R(WSRF)

Table HBB-I-14.10B-1

Stress Rupture Factors for Type 316 Stainless Steel Welded With SFA-5.22 E 308T and E 308L T; SFA-5.4 E 308 and E 308L; and SFA-5.9 ER 308 and ER 308L

SI Units

Temp., °C	10 h	30 h	100 h	300 h	1 000 h	3 000 h	10 000 h	30 000 h	100 000 h	300 000 h
450	1.00	0.98	0.96	0.96	0.96	0.95	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93
475	1.00	0.95	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.89	0.86	0.86	0.85	0.85
500	1.00	0.91	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.79	0.79	0.76	0.76
525	1.00	0.88	0.78	0.78	0.77	0.76	0.73	0.72	0.68	0.67
550	1.00	0.88	0.76	0.76	0.75	0.74	0.72	0.70	0.65	0.61
575	1.00	0.89	0.79	0.79	0.78	0.77	0.75	0.72	0.68	0.61
600	0.98	0.90	0.82	0.81	0.79	0.79	0.76	0.72	0.68	0.62
625	0.91	0.88	0.85	0.82	0.79	0.77	0.74	0.70	0.65	0.58
650	0.81	0.80	0.79	0.79	0.76	0.75	0.70	0.64	0.57	0.49
675	0.79	0.78	0.76	0.74	0.73	0.69	0.64	0.57	0.49	0.40
700	0.75	0.74	0.71	0.69	0.64	0.60	0.54	0.47	0.39	0.31

* Weld stress rupture factor in ASME is equivalent to J_r in RCC-MRx.

HITEP Platform for reliable integrity evaluation of welded joints

- ❖ **RCC-MRx**
- ❖ **ASME-HB**
- ❖ **ASME CC-2843**

'HITEP* Platform' for ETD evaluation

- ❖ ETD in creep range is challenging with complicated & tricky design rules.
- ❖ Web-based ETD evaluation platform developed by KAERI.

HITEP_RCC-MRx

HITEP_ASME-HB

HITEP : High Temperature design Evaluation Program

HITEP_RCC-MRx program

- ❖ ‘Design evaluation & defect assessment program’ as per RCC-MRx (V3.0)
- ❖ **HITEP** : **HI**gh **T**emperature design **E**valuation **P**rogram of RCC-MRx.

- ❖ **Three-Module Program (3-pillar)**

- **DBA (Design-By-Analysis : RB-3200)**
- **Pipe (RB-3600)**
- **A16** (defect assessment)

- ❖ HITEP_RCC-MRx has material option for Eurofer

HITEP_ASME-HB for ETD evaluation

❖ HITEP_ASME-HB (v1.0)

- Load-Controlled Limits
- Inelastic Strain Limits
- Creep-Fatigue Damage

HITEP_ASME-HB Ver. 1.0
Web-based Design Compatibility Assessment Program for HTR

KAERI

ASME III Div. 5

Subsection
HB - 3200
[2019Ed.]

KAERI 한국원자력연구원
Korea Atomic Energy Research Institute

Load-Controlled Limits

Inelastic Strain Limits

Creep-Fatigue Damage

User Manual

Load Controlled Limits

Material: 316SS

Service Level: Level A/B Level C Level D

UNIT: Mpa Pa

	σ_x	σ_y	σ_z	σ_{xy}	σ_{yz}	σ_{zx}
P_m	-0.033471					
P_b	-0.032295					
F	-0.033404					

Max. temp (°C): 545

Inelastic Strain Limits

Material: 316SS

Service Level: Level A/B Level C Level D

UNIT: Mpa Pa

	σ_x	σ_y	σ_z	σ_{xy}	σ_{yz}	σ_{zx}
P_m	-0.0334717	0.668092	0.609704	-0.0025025	0.00163485	-0.202877
P_b	-0.032295	-0.0644002	-0.0570343	0.0045647	-0.0038105	0.0143867
F	-0.0334044	0.0127496	0.00919904	0.0102848	-0.0086112	-0.0128064

[Load file] [Reset]

Creep-Fatigue Damage

Fatigue Damage

Material: 316SS

Design Number of Cycles(n): 30

Multiaxial adjustment factor(K_m): 1

Equiv. stress concentration factor(K):

	ϵ_x	ϵ_y	ϵ_z	γ_{xy}	γ_{yz}	γ_{zx}
Min.	0.00018287	0.00017917	0.0002264	5.29524E-0	6.48444E-0	-5.6062E-0
Max.	0.0059921	0.0058712	0.0074142	0.0017313	2.10535E-0	-1.82003E-

Creep Damage

Design Number of Cycles(n): 30

ΔT : 10

Total Hold Time(t_H): 15000 hour

Hold Temperature(T_{HT}): 545 °C

[OK] [Close]

Screen on 'Creep-Fatigue Damage'

HITEP_CC-2843 for class 2 ETD evaluation

❖ HITEP_CC-2843 (v1.0)

- Load-Controlled Limits
- Inelastic Strain Limits
- Creep-Fatigue Damage

The screenshot shows the 'Load Controlled Limits' dialog box. It has a blue title bar with a close button. The 'Material' is set to '316SS'. The 'Service Level' has three radio buttons: 'Level A/B', 'Level C', and 'Level D'. Below this is a label '---- < Primary Stress Component > ----'. The 'UNIT' has two radio buttons: 'Mpa' and 'Pa'. A table is displayed with the following data:

	σ_x	σ_y	σ_z	σ_{xy}	σ_{yz}	σ_{xz}
P_m	-0.033471	0.668092	0.609704	-0.002502	0.0016348	-0.202877
P_b	-0.032295	-0.064400	-0.057034	0.0045647	-0.003810	0.0143867
F	-0.033404	0.0127496	0.0091990	0.0102848	-0.008611	-0.012606

At the bottom right of the table area, there are buttons for '[Load file]' and '[Reset]'. Below the table, there are input fields for 'Max. temp (°C)' with the value '545' and 'Duration time' with the value '15000'. At the very bottom, there are buttons for '[OK]' and '[Close]'.

Screen on 'Load-Controlled Limits'

Application of design rules to welded Gen IV components & piping

❖ Target (example) systems & components

STELLA-2 (a large-scale sodium test facility, KAERI)

STELLA-2 (12m × 15m × 30m)
(under operation since Sept. 2020.)

Main components including heat exchangers

High-temperature Test Facility – STELLA*

❖ Phase 1: STELLA-1 (2012)

- Sodium component test loop for a [separate effect test](#)
- Thermal-hydraulic performance test for key sodium heat exchangers
 - Validation of HX** thermal-sizing and performance analysis codes
- Natural circulation flow tests in a closed loop piping system
 - Validation of flow transient analysis code

❖ Phase 2: STELLA-2 (2020)

An [Integral effect test](#) for verification of plant dynamic response

Synthetic review of key safety issues

Safety analysis code validation with the obtained test database

STELLA-2 Test section design and construction

Design validation using numerical simulation and experimental methodologies

*Sodium Thermal-Hydraulic Test Loop for Safety Simulation and Assessment

**HX: Heat Exchanger

STELLA-2 Overall Size (L x W x H): 18m x 15m x 30m

High-temperature components in STELLA

□ STELLA-1

- DHX (C)
- AHX
- Loop heater vessel

DHX

AHX

Loop heater vessel

□ STELLA-2

- Main vessel
- IHX
- Reservoir
- UHX
- IHTS piping

Main Vessel

IHX

Reservoir

UHX

IHTS piping

IHX with welded joints (FE model)

□ 3D FE Model

- Thermal / Stress element : Solid70/Solid185
- No. of nodes : 554286 EA
- No. of elements : 682745 EA

Detailed mesh on model IHX

IHX Full 3D FE model (material : Gr.91 steel)

IHX (Gr.91) - Analysis results

Temperature distribution

Distribution of stress intensities

IHX - Evaluation results from HITEP platform

	Criteria	Calculated	Allowable	Ratio	T (°C)
P-Type Damage	P_m (MPa)	5.52	190.2	0.047	550
	P_L (MPa)	5.22	285.2	0.031	
	$P_L + P_b$ (MPa)	5.05	285.2	0.013	
	$U_A(\Omega P_m)$	6.7442E-7	1	6.7442E-7	
	$U_A(P_m + \Phi P_b)$	4.0246E-7	1	4.0246E-7	
	$W_A(1.35P_m)$	2.1756E-6	1	2.1756E-6	
	$W_A[1.35(P_m + \Phi P_b)]$	1.3383E-6	1	1.3383E-6	
S-Type Damage	P_1 (MPa)	25.29	163.8	0.154	550
	P_2 (MPa)	24.19	245.7	0.098	
	Max ($P_L + P_b$) + ΔQ	120.93	378	0.320	
	$V_A (\Delta \epsilon)$	0.0007	1.00	0.001	
	$\epsilon_{plastic} + \epsilon_{creep} (1.25P_1)$	0.0048%	0.5%	0.01	
	$\epsilon_{plastic} + \epsilon_{creep} (1.25P_3)$	0.0041%	1.0%	0.0004	
	Fatigue Damage	negligible	See <i>r.h.s</i> Figure		
	Creep Damage	0.2168			

Section-C

Creep-Fatigue Damage evaluation results
as per ASME-HB and RCC-MRx

Main Vessel & Internal - Stress Analysis & C-F Damage

❖ MV & Int. (316L)

Stress intensities after Heat-up (4.25h)

❖ C-F damage @ Redan corner

Redan	ASME-HB	RCC-MRx
D_f	0.05690	0.00017
D_c	0.00010	0.01020

Reservoir – FE modeling

❖ Reservoir (304 SS)

□ 3D FE Model

- Thermal / Stress element : Solid70/Solid185
- No. of nodes : 43,706 EA
- No. of elements : 29,193 EA

□ Design Transients

Reservoir – Evaluation results

Creep-Fatigue Damage evaluation results (304SS)

Design Evaluations on High-Temperature Piping

❖ Hot leg piping system of STELLA-2 (316L)

▪ Design evaluation conducted as per

- RB-3600 (RCC-MRx)
- ASME B31.1

➤ ASME B31.1 Evaluation results

System	Subsystem	Code Equation	Node Point	Calculated Stress (MPa)	Ratio	Location
IHTS	Hot Leg	1 : S.L	295	40.3	0.697	Spring support
		2 : O.L	270	57.8	0.834	Tee
		3 : T.L	90	133	0.654	IHX nozzle
	Suction Leg	1 : S.L	2037	26.3	0.455	Spring support
		2 : O.L	2037	30.8	0.444	Spring support
		3 : T.L	2045	151.7	0.747	Elbow
	Cold Leg	1 : S.L	3740	16.5	0.286	IHX nozzle
		2 : O.L	3620	42.8	0.617	Elbow
		3 : T.L	3010	150.1	0.739	Reservoir nozzle

* S.L : Sustained Loads / O.L : Occasional Loads / T.L : Thermal Loads

No explicit consideration of creep effects

Non-conservative design might be obtained in case of long-term service in creep range.

Piping system of STELLA-2

Evaluation results from HITEP_RCC-MRx (piping)

➤ RB-3600 (RCC-MRx) evaluations using HITE_RCC-MRx

Evaluation Items		HITEP	Direct calculation
Load Controlled Limits	P_m (MPa)	6.15	6.15
	$P_m + P_b$ (MPa)	21.121	21.121
	$U_A(P_m)$	4.53875E-5	4.53175E-5
	$U_A(P_m + \Phi P_b)$	0.0025	0.0025
	$W_A(1.35P_m)$	1.1219E-5	1.1219E-5
	$W_A[1.35(P_m + \Phi P_b)]$	0.0009	0.0009
Inelastic Strain Limits	P_1 (MPa)	24.301	24.301
	P_2 (MPa)	45.036	45.036
	$(P_m + P_b) + q(j,j')$	117.15	117.15
	$\epsilon_{plastic} + \epsilon_{creep} (1.25P_1)$	0.0022 %	0.0023 %
	$\epsilon_{plastic} + \epsilon_{creep} (1.25P_3)$	0.0344 %	0.0344 %
Creep-Fatigue Damage	Fatigue Damage	9.1438E-7	9.1286E-7
	Creep Damage	0.1268	0.1268

Stress relaxation analysis result

Explicit consideration of creep effects : more reliable

HITEP_ASME-HB (1/4)

❖ Verification of HITEP_ASME-HB at welded joint

- Target component : Heat exchanger (DHX) in STELLA-1 test facility
- Material : P91 (9Cr-1Mo-1V)

DHX (STELLA-1)

Load Controlled Limits [X]

Material:

Service Level: Level A/B Level C Level D

---- < Primary Stress Component > ----

UNIT: Mpa Pa

	σ_x	σ_y	σ_z	σ_{xy}	σ_{yz}	σ_{zx}
P _m (MPa)	<input type="text" value="4.664"/>	<input type="text" value="-0.5826"/>	<input type="text" value="-0.09531"/>	<input type="text" value="-0.8301"/>	<input type="text" value="0.03377"/>	<input type="text" value="0.2137"/>
P _b (MPa)	<input type="text" value="0.1049"/>	<input type="text" value="-1.25"/>	<input type="text" value="0.1611"/>	<input type="text" value="0.1139"/>	<input type="text" value="0.0385"/>	<input type="text" value="0.01034"/>
F (MPa)	<input type="text" value="0.2526"/>	<input type="text" value="-0.5043"/>	<input type="text" value="0.2513"/>	<input type="text" value="0.01355"/>	<input type="text" value="-0.01974"/>	<input type="text" value="8.896E-5"/>

[Load file] | [Reset]

Max. temp (°C) Duration time

[OK] | [Close]

Input window of load-Controlled Stress Limits

Primary Stress Component

Max	σ_x	σ_y	σ_z	σ_{xy}	σ_{yz}	σ_{zx}
P _m	4.664	-0.5826	-0.09531	-0.8301	0.03377	0.2137
P _b	0.1049	-1.25	0.1611	0.1139	0.0385	0.01034
F	0.2526	-0.5043	0.2513	0.01355	-0.01974	8.896E-05

Secondary Stress Component

Max	σ_x	σ_y	σ_z	σ_{xy}	σ_{yz}	σ_{zx}
Q _m	-0.1046	-0.5762	3.621	-0.008535	-0.115	-0.04059
Q _b	0.841	-0.3663	-4.325	0.001163	-0.01123	-0.1278
F	0.05044	0.04466	-0.09585	-0.000301	0.0002517	0.002076

Min	σ_x	σ_y	σ_z	σ_{xy}	σ_{yz}	σ_{zx}
Q _m	-1.708	-0.6402	-2.339	0.7623	-0.8708	-0.3494
Q _b	0.03403	-0.001834	1.936	-0.5537	0.7626	0.2521
F	0.05364	-0.06639	0.2117	0.1663	-0.09258	-0.06886

Strain Component

	ϵ_x	ϵ_y	ϵ_z	γ_{xy}	γ_{yz}	γ_{zx}
Max	0.00631	0.00628	0.00581	0.000382	-7.18E-6	-0.000624
Min	0	0	0	0	0	0

Temp, Hold time, Cycle

Hold Temp	Hold Time	Number of Cycle	
510°C	15000	30	
Max. Extreme Temp	Min. Extreme Temp	Max. Wall Temp	Min. Wall Temp
485.5°C	401.7°C	508°C	316.9°C

HITEP_ASME-HB (2/4)

➤ Load-Controlled Stress Limits

- HITEP_ASME-HB results
- Independent evaluation results with Excel

Load Controlled Limits				
Load Controlled Limits (Level A/B)				
Material		9Cr-1Mo-1V		
Evaluation Items		Calculated	Limit value	Remark
Design Limit	$P_m \leq S_o$	5.5187 MPa	126.6 MPa	OK!!
	$P_L + P_b \leq 1.5S_o$	6.7694 MPa	189.9 MPa	OK!!
	$P_m < S_{mt}$	5.5187 Mpa	140.4 Mpa	OK!!
Load Controlled Limits	$P_L + P_b < KS_m$	6.7694 Mpa	214.50 Mpa	OK!!
	$(P_L + P_b / K_t) < S_t$ $K_t = (K + 1) / 2$	6.5149 Mpa	150.6 Mpa	OK!!
[Back] [Next]				

Output Window - Load Controlled Limits evaluation module

Comparison of the results

(unit : MPa)

	HITEP	Direct calculation
P_m	5.5187	5.5187
$P_L + P_b$	6.7694	6.7694
$P_L + P_b / K_t$	6.5149	6.5149
S_o	126.6	126.6
$1.5S_o$	189.9	189.9
S_{mt}	140.4	140.4
KS_m	214.5	214.5
S_t	150.6	150.6

HITEP_ASME-HB (3/4)

➤ Inelastic Strain Limits

- HITEP_ASME-HB input & output

Inelastic Strain Limits (Level A/B)			
Material		9Cr-1Mo-1V	
Evaluation Items	Calculated	Limit value	Remark
A1	$X + Y < S_u/S_y$	0.0274	0.8757 OK!!
A2	$X + Y < 1$	0.0274	1 OK!!
A3-1	$\sum(t_i/t_{id}) < 0.1$	0.0394	0.1 OK!!
A3-2	$\sum \epsilon_i < 0.2\%$	0.068	0.2 OK!!
A3-3	$(P_m + P_b + Q) < 3S_m$	5.67	409.81 OK!!
B1 & B2	$\sum \epsilon < 1\%$	0.1211	1 OK!!
B3	$\sum \epsilon < 1\%$	0.1211	1 OK!!

Input & output Window (Inelastic Strain Limits evaluation module)

Comparison of the results

(unit : MPa)

	HITEP	Direct calculation
$X + Y$	0.0274	0.0274
$\sum t_i/t_{id}$	0.0394	0.0394
$\sum \epsilon_i$	0.068	0.068
$P_m + P_b + Q$	5.67	5.67
$\sum \epsilon$	0.1211	0.1211
S_a/S_y	0.8757	0.8757
$3S_m$	409.81	409.81

HITEP_ASME-HB (4/4)

➤ Creep-Fatigue Damage Limits

- HITEP_ASME-HB input & output
- Independent evaluation results with Excel

Creep-Fatigue Damage

Material: 9Cr-1Mo-1V

$$\sum_{j=1}^p \left(\frac{n}{N_d} \right)_j + \sum_{k=1}^q \left(\frac{\Delta t}{T_d} \right)_k \leq D$$

	Calculated	Limit value	Check
Creep-Fatigue Damage	0.0024	0.0024	OK!!
Creep damage	0.0028	0.0028	OK!!

[Back] | [Next]

Creep-Fatigue Damage

Fatigue Damage

Material: 9Cr-1Mo-1V

Design Number of Cycles(n): 30

Multiaxial adjustment factor(K_s): 1

Eq. stress concentration factor(K): 1.134917526

---- < Strain component > ----

	ε _x	ε _y	ε _z	γ _{xy}	γ _{yz}	γ _{zx}
Min.	0	0	0	0	0	0
Max.	0.00631	0.00628	0.00581	0.000382	-0.0000071	-0.000624

Creep Damage

Design Number of Cycles(n): 30

ΔT: 0.1

Total Hold Time(t_h): 15000 hour

Hold Temperature(T_{HT}): 510 °C

[OK] | [Close]

[Creep-Fatigue Damage evaluation :Input Window]

Comparison of the results

	HITEP	Direct calculation
Fatigue Damage	0.0024	0.0024
Creep Damage	0.0028	0.0028

VI. Summary

- ❖ **Elevated Temperature Design (ETD) rules of the welded joints mainly for ASME-HB were reviewed and application of the rules were conducted for Gen IV components & piping system.**
 - **Treatment of welded joints in ETD rules were reviewed for ASME-HB & RCC-MRx.**
 - **Applications of ETD rules at welded joints to pressure boundary components and piping in next generation NPPs were conducted**
 - **For reliable and efficient ETD of pressure boundary components and piping, a web-based design evaluation platform of HITEP was developed by KAERI as follows;**
 - **HITEP_RCC-MRx (as per French ETD rules of RCC-MRx)**
 - **HITEP_ASME-HB (as per ASME-HB)**
 - **HITEP_CC-2843 (as per ASME CC-2843).**

THANK YOU

Hyeong-Yeon Lee (KAERI)

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Gap analysis and further development needs for HLM reactors – based on GEMMA WP4: *“Compatibility with heavy liquid metal and helium coolants”*

Caveat:

- The WP4 analysis, conclusions and Deliverables are still in progress.
- The observations/conclusions are preliminary.

K.-F. Nilsson

GEMMA Workshop on Welding Technologies for Generation IV, 4 October 2021

Outline

- **Background & Objectives**
- **GEMMA WP4 outline**
 - Objectives
 - Material & Test Programme
 - Results
- **Indications for gaps and further needs**

Heavy Liquid Cooled Nuclear Reactors

European projects

European, MYRRHA ADS –
Reactor, Three phases
Lead-Bismuth, ADS & Research
Reactor, SCK•CEN

European LFR Reactor ALFRED
Three stages demonstrator → FOAK,
FALCON (e.g. ENEA, ANSALDO)

SEALER: SMR LFR, Sweden

LeadCold & SMR AB

Gaps & Needs

- Lead and Eutectic Lead-Bismuth are aggressive environments
- Key Degradation mechanisms:
 - Liquid Metal Embrittlement (tensile, fracture toughness, creep)
 - Corrosion, erosion.
- To license the HLM reactors we need to demonstrate good compatibility between the HLM coolant and components/material
- Or in other words demonstrate fit-for-purpose

Gaps & Needs

- Regulatory system important for licensing approach
 - Prescriptive: Design Codes & Standards (RCC-MRx, ASME,.....) → HLM not included – Need to be developed, but how?
 - Performance Based -> Up to licensee, How to do it?

A comprehensive test programme is, and will be, the core irrespective if the regulation is prescriptive or performance based.

RCC-MRx AFCEN Design Code for Innovative Reactors 2018 Edition

RDG 2321 Use of the Code in innovative coolant environment

The operator (Prime Contractor) should follow the recommendations hereafter in order to insure structural integrity under operating conditions (mainly coolant chemistry):

- 1) The chosen material, in the chemistry controlled coolant, has the same behaviour as in air except for the depletion of the corrosion allowance,**
- 2) All failure modes inside or outside of the design Code shall be identified and addressed, flaws, local corrosion and local thinning will be detected before defects become critical(*), assuming a limited corrosion speed,**
- 3) The requested coolant parameters (composition, pressure, temperature, circulation speed...) will be satisfied all over the systems,
- 4) Failure of the chemistry control system that could cause high speed corrosion is detected and the grace time is sufficient to take corrective action.
- 5) These are satisfied including accepted and probable variations of both structural material and coolant.

2010 -2015: Ferritic-Martensitic steel, Grade 91, Reference material

Figure 23. Temperature dependence of total elongation of T91 measured in inert environment and in LBE at strain rate $5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The dashed red line depicts the minimum value in LBE.

In the MATTER project 2011 – 2015, it was shown that Grade 91 suffers from Liquid Metal Embrittlement in contact with HLM and therefore excluded as reference material

GEMMA Project (2017 – 2021)

- Austenitic steels, e.g. 316L appears to be corrosion resistant and does not embrittle in contact with HLM
- How about the welds as they may contain ferrite?
- Objective: a) Demonstrate compatibility austenitic steel/HLM for austenitic welded plates by Test Programme (WP4)
- → Basis for Engineering Data & Design Rules (WP2) → first steps for RCC-MRx Design Code

Fig. 6. Fatigue endurance of 316L tested in LBE at 300 and 400 °C, compared to air tests conducted at RT.

316L austenitic steels show very limited LME and good fatigue properties

GEMMA WP4 Materials

316L grade TIG NG welded coupons of 30 mm thickness

316L grade SAW welded coupons of 75 mm thickness

15-15Ti TIG welded coupons of 3 mm thickness

AFA steel bar 10x500 mm

(a) Coupon of 15-15Ti base material and
(b) thin plate welded of 15-15Ti

SAW weld, 75 mm

TIG weld, 30 mm

Test Programme in HLM (reported in June)

WP 4.1 Corrosion Tests

WP 4.2 Mechanical tests: SSRT, creep, Fracture Toughness

Organization	Tests	Material	Coolant
SCK CEN	SSRT, FT,	316L-SAW & TIG	LBE
CNRS	SSRT	15-15Ti, AFA	LBE/Pb
CIEMAT	SSRT, Creep	15-15Ti	Pb
CVR	FT	316L-TIG, 15-15Ti	Pb
ENEA	SSRT, Creep	316L-TIG	Pb
JRC	SSRT	316L-SAW	Pb

SSRT = Slow Strain Rate Tests
FT = Fracture Toughness Tests

Test Programme in HLM (reported in June)

SSRT – 316L TIG ENEA

Comparison_Base_Pb

Weld (longitudinal)

Cross Weld

• No LME on yield stress, ultimate strength or ductility
 • Larger scatter for weld than for base material

Comparis

ss weld material 550°C/5x10-6s-1

Test Programme in HLM (reported in June)

SSRT – 316L SAW JRC

- BM, 550°C: No LME on yield stress, ultimate strength (US) or ductility at 550°C
- WM, 400°C Some LME effect : Higher US and slightly lower ductility in Pb
- more scatter for WM

Test Programme in HLM (reported in June)

SSRT – 15-15Ti CIEMAT

- No LME on yield stress, ultimate strength (US) or ductility at 550°C
- Significantly higher US & YS for the BM than WM
- Similar scatter BM & WM

Test Programme in HLM (reported in June)

Creep – 316L TIG ENEA

Creep curves

- Tendency for higher creep rate in Pb than air
- Large inconsistencies in data;
- Minimum Creep rate
- No HLM effect; higher creep rate for WM & CW than BM

Test Programme in HLM (reported in June)

Creep – 15-15Ti CIEMAT

Creep curves

- Higher creep rate WM than BM
- Tendency for higher creep rate in Pb than air
- Large inconsistencies in data;

Test Programme in HLM (reported in June)

Fracture Toughness – 316L & 15-15Ti CVR

- Slightly higher FT in Pb, but no clear tendency
- Large scatter low R^2 values, (small specimens and environment)

LM Corrosion in LBE

Preliminary results

- Weld metal is more prone to the solution-based corrosion than annealed matrix of 316L steel **at elevated temperatures**
- Corrosion proceeds preferentially along the phase boundary of vermicular delta ferrite and austenite matrix
- Tests at lower temperatures and in flowing LBE don't show so big difference

The weld joint microstructure might enhance LMC in LBE

Static LBE

500 °C / 3000 hours / [O] < 10⁻¹⁰ mass%

Test programme LM Corrosion

ENEA 316L/15-15Ti, LMC, static Pb, 480°C, oxygen 10⁻⁹ -10⁻¹⁰ % wt.

- No oxidation after 10000h but dissolution
- BMs are more affected by dissolution than TIG and SAW welds

Gaps & Further Needs

- For HLM cooled reactors we need to demonstrate sufficient structural integrity and functioning for components with reference materials including the welds during long-term operation.
- 316L-ss appears not to be affected by LM embrittlement and corrosion under operational conditions, i.e. similar behaviour in HLM and air.
- In the GEMMA project there was not sufficient data to support this due to scatter and inconsistencies in data.

Urgent Needs

- Harmonized Test Protocols & Standards for testing in HLM environment
 - Detailed description & recording of test conditions and parameters;
 - Pre-exposure;
 - Measurement and monitoring during test in HLM;
 - Assess testing of small-sized specimen in HLM;
 - Statistical Test Planning for Optimized Test Programme.

Further Needs

- Test data representative for in-service conditions
- Understanding of accelerated tests and extrapolation to in-service conditions
 - Supporting models at appropriate length and time scales for different degradation mechanisms
 - Supporting microstructural analysis
- Other tests, e.g. creep-fatigue
- Engineering Data & Design Rules codified in Design Codes
- Mid/Long Term: Development of new material solutions, AFA, coatings, overlay welds.....

Keep in touch

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Thank you

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**Residual stress measurement
techniques**

HERZLICH WILLKOMMEN

am Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin

Based on diagram from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Residual_stress

Raman

Factors

Expense	Spatial resolution
Availability of method	Availability of expertise
Accuracy needed	Speed of measurement/results
Destructive	Non-destructive
Size of specimen	Weight of specimen
Thickness of specimen	Shape of specimen
Material to be measured	Accessibility of the region of interest
Texture	Grain size
Laboratory based	Remotely 'on location'
Surface	Bulk
Amount of plastic deformation	More that I have not thought of?

In general the uncertainty of a particular material is proportional to the Elastic/ Young's modulus. This is the case for most residual stress measuring techniques.

Diffraction techniques depend also on counting statistics which make the measurement time dependent

Material	Bulk elastic modulus GPa	Typical quoted uncertainty MPa
Aluminium	80	8-12
Titanium	116	10-15
Steel	200	20-30

EXAMPLE ALUMINIUM IMPELLER

Neutron
Diffraction

Factors	
Expense	Spatial resolution
Availability of method	Availability of expertise
Accuracy needed	Speed of measurement/results
Destructive	Non-destructive
Size of specimen	Weight of specimen
Thickness of specimen	Shape of specimen
Material to be measured	Accessibility of the region of interest
Texture	Grain size
Laboratory based	Remotely 'on location'
Surface	Bulk
Amount of plastic deformation	More that I have not thought of?

EXAMPLE ALUMINIUM IMPELLER

Neutron
Diffraction

Techniques	
X-rays	?
Neutrons	Yes
Magnetic	No
Ultrasonic	?
Hole drilling	?
Contour	?

TG7 Specimen, EB weld and Repair weld

TG7 Repair Weld Longitudinal direction $x=+8\text{mm}$ Neutrons versus hole drilling

TG7 Repair Weld Transverse direction $x=+8\text{mm}$ Neutrons versus Hole drilling

X-ray energy ranges.

Can be angular or energy dispersive

Type	Energy range	
'Standard lab X-rays'	5–20 keV	Available at HZB!
Advanced X-ray (LEDDI)	Up to 60 keV	Available at HZB!
Metal jet	Up to 160 keV	Available at HZB!
Synchrotron	80–1000 keV	

Surface measurements

I.A. Denks, Ch. Genzel, Enhancement of energy dispersive residual stress analysis by consideration of detector electronic effects, Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms, Volume 262, Issue 1, 2007, EDDI/E3

Synchrotron measurements

Neutron measurements

EXAMPLE 4: ROUND ROBIN -USING MULTIPLE METHODS: TG4

Mike C. Smith, Ann C. Smith, Carsten Ohms, Robert C. Wimpory,
 The NeT Task Group 4 residual stress measurement and analysis round robin on a three-pass slot-welded plate specimen, International Journal of Pressure Vessels and Piping, Volume 164, 2018, Pages 3-21,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpvp.2017.09.003>.

EXAMPLE 5: USING MULTIPLE METHODS- SHOT PEENED SURFACE

Closing Remarks

List what is needed for your measurement

List characteristics of specimen

Go through 'Factors influencing decision making'
check list

Rule out the unfeasible/unsuitable methods

Get more advice/information from your friendly experts.

Italian National Agency for New Technologies,
Energy and Sustainable Economic Development

High-resolution neutron diffraction measurements

*GEMMA Online Workshop on Welding technologies for Generation-IV systems,
their qualifications and residual stress modelling*

Monday-Tuesday, 4-5 October 2021

R. Coppola – Enea-Casaccia, Roma, Italy

outcome RESTRESS experiment

**GEMMA stress measurements on 316 TIG
weld before and **after PWHT****

RESTRESS experiment

hybrid laser beam and gas metal arc weld (LB - GMAW) of AISI316LN austenitic steel (17.8 Cr, 12.3 Ni, 1.7 Mn, 2.4 Mo, 0.3 Si Fe bal wt%)
size 220 x 160 x 15 mm³

316LN steel LB – GMAW weld (top) and comb-like unstrained reference sample (bottom), with investigated points
gauge volume 2 x 2 x 2 mm³

RESTRESS experiment

below weld cap

at mid-thickness

at weld root

Stresses as a function of the distance from the weld center in AISI316LN LB – GMAW along lines below weld cap, at mid-thickness, at weld root.

neutron diffraction measurements at E3 HZB, Dr. R. C. Wimpory local contact

P. Agostini, G. Barbieri, R. Coppola, M. Moncada, C. Ohms, R. C. Wimpory, *Stress Distributions in P91 Martensitic Steel and in AISI 316 LN Steel Welds for Gen IV Nuclear Applications*, J. of Surf. Investigation (2020), 14, pp. S25-S30

TIG NG 316L(N) weld (prepared by CEA)

size: 305 mm long, 295 mm wide and 24 mm thick

mapping: at mid-length across the weld, 6 mm and 14 mm depth, inside the weld

un-strained references: rod-shaped samples obtained in BM and weld from 5 mm thick slice cut from the original 316L(N) TIG narrow gap weld

TIG NG 316L(N) weld (prepared by CEA)

Table 1 – Chemical composition (wt%, Fe bal) for base and filler material

Base material AISI 316 L(N)

C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Mo	Ni	N	Cu	Co	B
0.026	0.31	1.74	0.025	0.001	17.27	2.54	12.13	0.069	0.29	0.09	0.0004

Filler material solid wire 18Cr-12Ni-2Mo

C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Mo	Ni	N	Cu	Co	Al	Nb	Ti	B	Ta
0.044	0.513	1.318	0.013	0.0033	18.236	1.953	11.526	0.064	0.097	0.001	0.006	0.001	0.001	0.0004	0.005

Experimental layout

incoming neutron beam

incoming neutron beam

Si(004), $\langle 311 \rangle$ refl., $\lambda = 1.47 \text{ \AA}$

selected gauge volumes (X x Y x Z)

T: 2 x 2 x 10 mm³ **L:** 3 x 3 x 2 mm³ **N:** 2 x 2 x 10 mm³

STRESS-SPEC instrument, FRM II, local contact Dr. M. Hofmann
ENEA-TUM industrial agreement

Experimental uncertainties^{1, 2} and protocol

sample positioning accuracy: ± 0.1 mm

entry scans to account for 4° bending of the weld

$\Delta\theta$: $\pm 0.004^\circ$ $\Delta \epsilon$: ± 42 $\mu\text{m/m}$ $\Delta\sigma$: ± 12 MPa

1) R.S. Ramadhan, S. Cabeza, T. Pirling, S. Kabra, M. Hofmann, J. Rebelo Kornmeier, A.M. Venter, D. Marais, *Quantitative analysis and benchmarking of positional accuracies of neutron strain scanners*, Nucl. Instr. Method. 999 (2021) 165230

2) C. Randau, U. Garber, H.-G. Brokmeier, *StressTextureCalculator: a software tool to extract texture, strain and microstructure information from area-detector measurements*, J. Appl. Cryst. 44 (2011) 641-646

the sample was oscillated to mitigate grain size spurious effects

d_0 for BM: average in the BM reference rod

d_0 for weld: measuring weld reference rod in each location and direction

$E_{(311)} = 183.6$ MPa, $\nu_{(311)} = 0.306$

TIG-NG 316L(N) weld as received - stresses

6 mm depth

14 mm depth

stresses as a function of the distance from the weld centre, at 6 mm and 14 mm depth below the surface of the weld for the three measurement directions: longitudinal (circles, blue), transverse (squares, red), normal (triangles, green).

TIG-NG 316L(N) weld as received- stresses

longitudinal

transverse

normal

comparison of longitudinal , transverse and normal stresses at 6 mm and 14 mm depth, inside the weld and the HAZ

TIG-NG 316L(N) weld as received - stresses

stresses as a function of the distance from the weld cap in the centre of the weld, for the three measurement directions: longitudinal (circles, blue), transverse (squares, red), normal (triangles, green).

TIG-NG 316L(N) weld as received - FWHM

6 mm depth

14 mm depth

inside the weld

FWHM (°), without correction for instrument background:

**increase within ± 20 mm from weld centre related to plastic deformation
no change inside the weld, below the cap**

Stress field comparison RESTRESS vs GEMMA welds

RESTRESS weld data:
mid-thickness,
8.5 mm below weld cap

GEMMA weld data:
6 mm below weld cap

Measurement TIG-NG 316L(N) weld after PWHT

Delayed due to sample preparation and unavailability of FRM II

A second high-resolution neutron diffraction experiment, on the PWHT TIG NG weld, is in progress at the POLDI instrument, at SINQ-PSI (www.psi.ch/en/sinq/poldi), in the frame of an industrial agreement between the ENEA and the ANAXAM (APPLIED MATERIAL ANALYTICS USING NEUTRON AND SYNCHROTRON RADIATION) (www.anaxam.ch)

***Based on preliminary test, no need to cut the weld, expected gauge volumes:
L 3.8x3.8x3.8 mm³, T and N 15x8x8 mm³***

Results expected by mid October 2021

PWHT TIG-NG 316L(N) stress mapping

Summary

good correlation between RESTRESS and GEMMA weld results

GEMMA TIG weld is narrow-gap also from micro-structure viewpoint

safety concern from high L stress within ± 20 mm from weld centre

work to be completed by stress mapping after PWHT

ADDITIONAL SLIDES

strain and stress determination

Strain:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{d(T) - d_0(T)}{d_0(T)}$$

d_0 un-strained lattice parameter

Stress tensor:

$$\sigma_x = \frac{E}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} [(1-\nu)\varepsilon_x + \nu(\varepsilon_y + \varepsilon_z)]$$

$$\sigma_y = \frac{E}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} [(1-\nu)\varepsilon_y + \nu(\varepsilon_x + \varepsilon_z)]$$

$$\sigma_z = \frac{E}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} [(1-\nu)\varepsilon_z + \nu(\varepsilon_x + \varepsilon_y)]$$

POLDI: Pulse OverLap Diffractometer

-time-of-flight (TOF) thermal neutron diffractometer, dedicated to materials science applications

- angular dependence of the TOF is used as additional parameter for data analysis

-intensity is given by the duty cycle of the chopper but the resolution by the chopper speed

-high intensity and good resolution can be achieved simultaneously

GEMMA Workshop on Welding technologies for Generation-IV systems, their qualifications and residual stress modelling –

Overview of the activities of the European Network on Neutron Techniques Standardization for Structural Integrity [NeT]

C. Ohms

JRC-Petten

Outline

- About NeT
- NeT Task Groups
- Output of NeT and NeT spinoffs
- Examples of technical results
- Conclusion

About NeT

19.5 years

NeT

2002 - 2021

About NeT

- A research collaboration based on a non-binding, non-written agreement between partners sharing an interest in the agreed research (Task Groups)
- Not externally funded (so far)
- Internal funding takes place
- About 25 participants today, over the years around 40 contributors
- More than 10 partners in NeT since 2002
- Past contributions also from Australia, South-Korea, Japan and the US

About NeT

- NeT partners are: research centres, neutron sources, universities, industry, consulting companies
- <https://www.net-network.eu/>
- 9 Task Groups so far
- Focus on residual stress measurement and simulation for model cases of welds for nuclear applications

NeT Task Groups (TGs)

- TG1: Single Bead-on-Plate Weldment (Stainless Steel)
- TG2: Letter Box Repair Weld (Ferritic Steel)
- TG2: Auxiliary Specimen (Ferritic Steel)
- TG3: Small Angle Neutron Scattering in support of NeT
- TG4: 3-Pass Slot Weld (Stainless Steel)

NeT Task Groups (TGs)

- TG5: Edge Welded Beam (Ferritic Steel)
- TG6: 3-Pass Slot Weld (Ni alloy)
- TG7: Electron beam weld on a high strength Al alloy
- TG8: 5-Pass Slot Dissimilar Weld (Ni alloy) on Ferritic Steel
- TG9: Additive manufacturing by weld bead deposition

Output of NeT and spinoffs

- In the order of 100 scientific publications
- 2 dedicated issues of IJPVP
- Contribution to ~10 PhD theses
- Contribution to standardization (ISO 21432 on ND, ISO/TS 18166)
- Probably the most comprehensive welding residual stress round robins (measurement and simulation) one can find
- Inputs to welding simulation chapter of R6 defect assessment procedure

Output of NeT and spinoffs

- Surface machining stress evolution
- Phase transformation modelling
- Modelling of thermo-mechanical cycles
- Materials data
- Shift of gauge volume centroid in through thickness direction
- “Layzian” average

Examples of technical results

- TG1: the impact of parameter and procedure choices on spread of simulation results

Examples of technical results

- TG2 Aux: measurements by different techniques or at different facilities

C. Ohms, R.C. Wimpory, D. Neov, M. Hofmann, M. Turski, R. Haigh, M. Fitzpatrick, L. Edwards, "Residual Stress Measurements in a Three-Bead Slot Weld in a 20 mm Carbon Steel Plate", in: Proceedings of ASME PVP 2009, Prague, Czech Republic, July 26-30, 2009, ASME, CD Publication, 2009, Order No. I821CD, ISBN 978-0-7918-3854-9

Examples of technical results

- TG4: finding a robust measurement average and identifying outliers

Examples of technical results

- TG5: not perfect in phase transformation region and fusion zone

Examples of technical results

- TG6: simulation(s) compared to measurement average - longitudinal

NOTE: The presentation given at the Workshop contained a different version of this plot. This version is unpublished, therefore it has been replaced with the version shown here.

Examples of technical results

- TG8: five weld beads Ni52 in a slot in an 18MND5 ferritic steel plate

NOTE: The presentation given at the Workshop contained the first residual stress measurement data as presented during a meeting of the NeT partners. The data shown had been unpublished at the time of compiling these proceedings, and are therefore replaced by an illustration of the specimen used in this Task Group.

Conclusion

- NeT is a prolific research collaboration in WRS area; it has been active for almost 20 years
- Individual partners interest in common research keeps it going
- Impact on residual stress aspect of integrity assessment, impact on R6 code
- Impact on standardization and harmonization
- Some scientific/engineering “spin-offs”
- We hope to be around for several more years
- Interested parties are welcome – requirement is technical contribution to agreed activities

Thank you!

Lessons learned in NeT on weld residual stress analysis – impact on safety, defect assessments, and codification

or

“What does NeT teach us about measuring and predicting residual stresses and then using them to predict crack driving forces?”

GEMMA workshop

4th-5th October 2021

Mike Smith,

Professor of Welding Technology

the University of Manchester

Contents of talk

- NeT and the development of the R6 weld modelling guidelines
- Implications of NeT TG4 for RS measurement procedures
- Implications of NeT TG4 for RS simulation procedures
- Implications of NeT TG4 for defect tolerance assessments

How does NET's mission relate to defect assessment in operating plant?

- NeT was founded in 2002
- Its mission is to develop experimental and numerical techniques and standards for the reliable characterisation of residual stresses in structural welds
- Back in 2002, Net's first task group, TG1, used a welded benchmark developed in the UK to support underpinning research for an AGR boiler safety case
- British Energy (now EDF) needed accurate estimates of residual stresses in finite length repair welds
- This need covered both measured and predicted stresses, since both are required to be in adequate agreement before an assessment using R6 is acceptable
- Residual stresses were intended to be used in defect tolerance assessments
- The insights from NeT TG1 formed part of the background to the development of the R6 weld modelling guidelines

Assessment of the
Integrity of Structures
Containing Defects

The Engineering state of the art: R6 weld modelling guidelines, 2009 onwards

- Developed in the UK to predict and manage reheat cracking in AISI 316H welds in AGR's
 - Conventional arc welds (not narrow gap, no beam processes)
 - Residual stress and subsequent creep relaxation
 - No interest in weld process optimisation
 - No interest in distortion per se
 - No need to explicitly model microstructure development
- **Detailed step by step validation is a key part of the procedure**
 - **Is the thermal load sufficiently accurate?**
 - **Are the residual stresses reliable?**
- These took account of what we learned in NeT TG1
- We can use NeT TG4 as a worked example of this process

The R6 weld modelling procedure

1. Define analysis objectives
2. Collect input data
3. Consider resources available
4. Decide weld modeling approach
5. Create Finite Element model
6. Perform thermal analysis
7. Perform mechanical analysis
8. Validate analysis
9. Perform sensitivity studies

The NeT TG4 international benchmark

AISI 316L(N) plate containing three superimposed TIG beads laid into a slot

- Finite length weld with strongly 3D residual stress distribution
- Simple structural boundary conditions
- Multi-pass weld – several TMF cycles
- Significant volume of weld metal – need to handle property development
- **No SSPT**

Moving heat source finite element predictions are feasible

Easy to move around the world for measurements

Organization of TG4 measurement round robin

- Measurement and simulation round robins are carried out independently and in parallel.
- **Measurements round robin controlled by detailed protocol**
 - Recommended best-practice experimental procedure
 - Measurement lines and points
 - Reporting requirements
- Welded TG4 specimens accompanied by unwelded control specimen (machined, heat-treated, but no weld – should be stress free)
- d_0 specimens manufactured for parent material, top of weld (final pass) and bottom of weld (first pass)
- Slices made available for comb manufacture and $\sin^2\Phi$ measurements

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Contents of measurement protocol

TG4 Measurements programme

- Neutron and high-energy X-ray diffraction measurements made on three specimens:
 - Nine instruments in total
 - Fourteen individual sets of measurements
 - Several re-measurements
- iDHD measurements made on two specimens
- Contour measurements made on at more than 3 specimens (two transverse, one longitudinal)
- DIC surface strains, ultrasonics, ICHD
- ND measurements also made on a fourth “batch 2” specimen

Diffraction-based TG4 measurements on batch 1 TG4 specimens

Laboratory	Instrument	Specimens	Type
1	FRM II	1-1A, 3-1A	Reactor
2	HZB-E3	3-1A twice	Reactor
3	ESRF (ID15A)	1-1A, 3-1A	Synchrotron X-Ray
4	VULCAN	3-1A	Pulsed
4*	ENGIN-X	3-1A twice	Pulsed
5	SALSA	1-1A twice	Reactor
6	Kowari	2-1A	Reactor
7	Poldi	1-1A	Pulsed

Only Laboratory 2 and Laboratory 3 made measurements in the unwelded control specimen

The first set of measurements made at ENGIN-X were withdrawn

Measured longitudinal stresses - best estimate and +/- 1 SD

Longitudinal stresses – Diffraction-based measurements

Observations on TG4 Diffraction residual stress measurements

- The large diffraction data set allows for a robust best-estimate of the residual stress profile
- The calculated uncertainties are of the order +/- 20-40 MPa – and are highest near surfaces and in “pass 1” weld metal.
- These are approximately half those calculated before elimination of systematic errors
- The measurements may be classed as “consensus + outliers”
- Clear outliers: first ENGIN-X, and both SALSA measurements
 - SALSA has unrealistic normal stresses
 - First ENGIN-X did not, but was an obvious outlier
- Some of the “consensus” measurements also fall outside the overall uncertainty band
- ***How would we have fared if we could only afford one measurement?***
- ***Would we have done better to go with strain relief measurements?***

Longitudinal stresses –strain relief measurements

Lessons from TG4 measurements round robin

- We cannot rely on a single set of measurements made using a single technique
- Typical uncertainty of measurements at a single diffraction instrument much higher than the fitting error normally quoted
- All techniques as currently practiced struggle to quantify systematic errors
- Measurements are “user dependent” – no substitute for the right people, following the right procedures, in the right place.
- Plenty of “best practice” recommendations
- ***The R6 recommendation of measurement using two independent techniques with different characteristic errors is shown to be sound***

TG4 simulation round robin – control of uncertainty

- Welding temperature transients were well characterised
 - Accurate 3D MHS thermal solutions were readily obtained
- Structural boundary conditions were straightforward
 - No simplification of the structure required
 - Simple free boundary conditions
- Major free variables
 - Material properties
 - Hardening behaviour
 - High temperature response
 - “unknown unknowns”
- Simulations of plant welds seldom have these luxuries

NeT TG4 thermocouple arrays

Three specimens were instrumented.

The mid-length array design was deliberately redundant, so up to six individual thermocouples produced equivalent responses – minimising the impact of scatter in the measured responses

RMS errors in predicted temperature rises at mid-length thermocouple arrays for pass 3, NeT TG4

Typical thermocouple responses at a mid-length thermocouple – NeT TG4

Predicted longitudinal stresses – all simulations

Typical cyclic response of AISI 316 austenitic steel

- The material cyclically hardens or softens
- The yield stress in a given direction is reduced by prior plastic flow in the reversed direction.
- This is the Bauschinger effect
- These tests are expensive to perform
- The response depends on the strain range

Isotropic, kinematic and mixed hardening

Consider a 2D stress state – the von Mises yield surface is an ellipse initially centred on the origin

In isotropic hardening the yield surface only expands – the expansion is a function of the equivalent plastic strain PEEQ, which is a SCALAR

In kinematic hardening the yield surface translates – the position of its centre is determined by the backstress \mathbf{a} , which is a TENSOR

In mixed hardening the yield surface expands and translates

This only matters if the loading is reversed – all three hardening models can describe a simple tensile test

Effect of basic hardening model on longitudinal stresses

The problem of weld metal

- Austenitic weld metal shows similar cyclic hardening behaviour to parent material
- Austenitic welds show a hardness gradient from the root (hardest, longest plastic path, most cycles), to the last capping pass (softest, shortest plastic path, one cool-down cycle)
- But, when we test weld metal to develop its mechanical properties, we need to get the starting condition right to match the “as-solidified” condition of a weld bead.
- The weld metal used for small scale testing should be free of work-hardening.
- How do we achieve this?

Evaluating relevant mechanical properties for austenitic weld metal

Multi-pass weld pad

Single or two pass weld

Multi-pass weld

As-welded condition

“spike-annealed”

Solution-treated

Conventional isothermal tensile and cyclic tests

DIC or ESPI cross-weld testing

Effect of fabrication route on 0.2% proof stress of AISI 316L weld metal

Effect of weld metal “starting point” (yield stress) on longitudinal stress

Cyclic hardening behaviour of AISI 316L solution-treated two-pass TIG weld metal

Effect of optimized mixed hardening models, longitudinal stresses

The state of the art in “simple” weld modelling of austenitic steels

- Repeatable, reliable RS measurements still present a considerable challenge
- We can get the thermal solutions right
- It is possible to produce accurate weld residual stress predictions using well controlled simulation procedures, including:
 - Strict adherence to weld modeling guidelines
 - Formalised heat source modeling tools
 - Optimised mixed hardening constitutive models
 - Weld metal test data for a state that approximates a just-deposited bead
- It is still possible to get it wrong, and produce plausible rubbish
 - Trained and experienced analysts are essential
- Sensitivity studies and validation are not optional:
 - Sensitivity studies allow key variables to be identified and bounded
 - The R6 procedure does not allow the use of un-validated finite element predictions of weld residual stresses

The end-product – a defect tolerance assessment

What effect does uncertainty in the measured and predicted stresses have on the SIF for postulated defects?

What performance criteria should we apply?

How do the stresses in TG4 compare with an R6 “level 2” profile?

How do the stresses in TG4 compare with an R6 “level 2” profile?

Comparison of “best” simulations with “measured” SIF uncertainty

SIF trajectories for transverse defects

Comparison of “best” simulations with “measured” SIF uncertainty

Impact of residual stress uncertainty on predicted SIF trajectories

- R6 proposed a "SIF within 95% of measured SIF" acceptance criterion based upon TG1 experience
- This is unworkable for TG4
 - If uncritically applied it could force the use of analyses already known to be incorrect merely because they are conservative
 - It ignores uncertainty in measurements
- A more realistic approach may be:
 - Use FE models that already pass appropriate acceptance criteria
 - (qualitative review, RMS stress, Linearised stress)
 - Increase the residual stresses input into the SIF solution
 - For TG4 we could add a membrane stress based upon the measurement uncertainty
 - Otherwise we follow R6 advice and perform sensitivity study on material yield strength

“All models are wrong, but some models are useful”

George Box (statistician), 1976, 1978

Generation IV Materials Maturity (GEMMA) project

Residual stress modelling for component design and safety/integrity assessments according to RCC-MRx requirements

Diogo Gonçalves
CEA SACLAY, DES/ISAS/DM2S/SEMT/LTA

In contribution with: Serge PASCAL, from CEA; Viorel DEACONU and Vasile RADU, from RATEN ICN; Adib BECKER, Wei SUN, Suo LI and Chris BENNETT, from University of Nottingham

Workshop on Welding technologies for Generation-IV systems, their qualifications and residual stress modelling
05-10-2021

RCC-MRx Design Code [AFCEN]

Improving safety of the new generations of nuclear reactors → the French design and construction rules for mechanical components of nuclear installations, **RCC-MRx, has been continuously updated**, including Tome 4, concerning welding operations and their implementation

Examples

2015 → integration of the control and welding processes of aluminum, with regard to components operating at high temperatures (design rules, welded joints, material properties), basing on the RJH (experimental reactor) construction.

2015-2018 → data on the Eurofer material, used by the Fusion community.

The code progress is based **only** on the experience feedback, not accounting for numerical simulations [*AFCEN : Qualification des outils de calcul scientifique utilisés dans la démonstration de sûreté nucléaire – première barrière. AFCEN, afnor édition, 03 2019*]

However scientific computing results **can be used** for assisting the welding operation, and predict materials changings related to the welding process (temperature gradients, material deformation, residual stresses, etc.)

OBJETIF → RECOMMENDATIONS FOR WELDING SIMULATIONS

Welding numerical simulation

GEMMA
project
results

Welding problem

- ❑ GEMMA project framework
- ❑ Specimen preparation and residual stress measurements
 - 400 mm long x 300 mm wide x 24 mm thick plates of 316L stainless steels
 - 4 TIG (Tungsten Inert Gas) specimens: U groove with 18-12-2 filler metal
 - 4 SMAW (Shielded Metal Arc Welding) specimens: V groove with 19-12-2 filler metal

MANUFACTURING OF 4 TIG WELDED SPECIMENS

Specimen identification	Radiographic testing (RCC-MRx acceptance criteria N1Rx (RS7714.31))	
	Welding defect	Conform
G17-TNG-2	No defects	Yes
G18-TNG-3	No defects	Yes
G18-TNG-4	No defects	Yes
G18-TNG-5	No defects	Yes

Run	Layer	v (mm/min)	I (A)	U (V)	P_L (kJ/mm)
1	1	80	205	9.2	1.4145
2	2	100	245	9.8	1.4406
3	3	120	265	9.6	1.272
4	4	120	265	9.6	1.272
5	5	120	265	9.6	1.272
6	6	120	265	9.6	1.272
7	7	120	265	9.6	1.272
8	8	120	265	9.6	1.272
9	9	120	265	9.6	1.272
10	10	120	180	10	0.9
11	10	120	180	10	0.9

Metallographic examinations on cross sections \Rightarrow no defect

Macrographs of the TIG specimens and welding parameters

Geometry of the welded joint

→ Take into account the correct dimensions of all components, including the welding passes

(a) The mock-up dimensions are 400 mm long x 300 mm wide. Six thermocouples were implemented in the specimen. They are located at 5 mm depth, in holes of 1 mm diameter and angle of 30°. (b) Chamfer scheme for the TIG specimen. (c) Chamfer filling scheme, specimen G17 - TNG – 2

2D Calculation → 11 passes → 16371 nodes, 5160 quadratic FE

Thermal modelling

- It is necessary to correct choose the better **thermal and initial boundary conditions**. These concern the outside temperature, the interpass temperature, convective heat exchange, as well as radiative transfers.
- Convective heat transfer: $T_0 = 20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $h = 25 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$
- Radiative heat transfer: $\epsilon = 0.8$
- Thermophysical parameters → Minh Le, « *Approches expérimentale et numérique de la fissuration à chaud dans les soudures en acier inoxydable* », PhD Dissertation, Université de Bretagne Sud, 2014.

Schematization of the thermal boundary heat transfer (red lines) applied to the steel sheets (dark gray area).

Thermal modelling

- **Metal filling modelling:** two different techniques are often used to model the addition of filler material. The “**quiet elements method**” consists in activate the elements, by changing the material properties when they reach the melting temperature (passing from degraded to nominal properties). For the “**inactive method**”, the elements are not part of the system of equations until they are activated

Activation of FE during the welding simulation. Material properties changes from degraded to nominal when the elements are activated

Thermal modelling

- **Heat input modelling:** for 2D and 3D calculations, the heat input can be modeled by an equivalent heat source. In this case, the coefficient of efficiency, η , must be adjusted using thermal data obtained during the welding process.

(left) Position of the six thermocouples were implemented in the specimen. (middle) Comparison between experimental and computed thermograms for welding runs 7 and 9. (right) Comparison between experimental and computed maximum temperatures

Metallurgical modelling

- **Not considered for the 316L stainless steel** since it do not experience significant volumetric phase transformation.
- Many models are proposed in the literature, allowing predicting phase transformation. In this case, the phase transformation kinetics of a specific material must be known.

Comparison between the phases present in the computed HAZ with those observed experimentally for a Fe-10Cr martensitic steel [Roux 2007]

Mechanical modelling

- **Constitutive laws:** for the prediction of residual stresses, it is recommended to use elastoplastic models, without time-dependent plasticity [Depradeux and Coquard, 2008], with kinematic or mixed strain hardening [Murasnky et al., 2012], specific to base and filler metals

It is advisable to adjust the parameters of these models, and in particular the elastic limit, the coefficient of thermal expansion and the Young's modulus using reliable experimental data

- Chaboche elastoplastic model, with mixed strain hardening.
- Materials parameters were taken from [Murasnky et al., 2012]

Mechanical modelling

- **Annealing modeling:** the very high temperatures ($T > 0,75T_m$) locally applied during the welding process results in almost complete evanescence of the material hardening. The “annealing phenomenon” have a strong influence on the stress evolution.
- Many models accounts for material annealing [S. Li, D. Deng, A.A. Becker, W. Sun, D. Goncalves, *The role of annealing effect in the formation of welding residual stresses and its modelling in austenitic stainless steel joints*, Submitted. (2021)].
- In this work, annealing was simulated by a **straightforward procedure**: when the temperature reaches the threshold-annealed temperature ($T_{anneal} = 1000\text{ °C}$), the state variables were reset to zero, resulting in the consequently stress relaxation.

Mechanical modelling

- **Boundary conditions:** clamping elements of the welded component. We must ensure that the model does not lead to an excessive concentration of stresses.
 - clamping on both sides, with nodal constraint in all nodes positioned in a length of 10 mm on the top and on the bottom of the geometry, preventing the displacement in the Y direction
 - the first node on the bottom left corner is block in the X direction, preventing rigid body motion

Simulation

- 1 pass = 3600 s → total of 650 computation steps → 500 steps for the first 5s of simulation (heat source application)
- Total computation time: ~ 2h50

Post-treatment

Cast3M

Transverse stress

Cast3M

Longitudinal stress

Cast3M

Displacement along Y (x5)

Post-treatment → Validation

- Validation with respect to experimental results obtained on welded specimens
 - Comparison between the observed macrograph of the weld cross-section and the computed melted zone ($T > 1400\text{ °C}$)

(left) Maximum temperature higher than the melting temperature (1400 °C). Comparison to the weld cross-section macroscopy. (right) Maximum temperature reached during the numerical simulation

Post-treatment → Validation

- Validation with respect to experimental results obtained on welded specimens
 - Experimental measurements using the contour method were carried out at Aalto University, in Finland

Profiles of transverse (dashed lines) and longitudinal (solid lines) stresses along the weld center line

Post-treatment → Validation

- Validation with respect to experimental results obtained on welded specimens
 - Experimental measurements using the contour method were carried out at Aalto University, in Finland

Profiles of longitudinal stresses along the weld center line at 10 mm (blue lines) and 18 mm (red lines) height

Post-treatment → Validation

- Validation with respect to other FE software (benchmark)

Longitudinal stress

CONCLUSION

Currently, the RCC-MRx does not take into account numerical predictions. However, the numerical results can assist in the welding operation, by predicting the behavior of welded joints: deformation, residual stress and metallurgical characteristics.

A model was proposed, using the Cast3M software, but also Abaqus (UNot) and Ansys (RATEN ICN):

- i) By benchmarking the computations of the three software, very similar residual stress fields are found;
- ii) The predictions are also in good agreement in comparison to experimental measurements.

For reliable simulations, several steps must be respected. The validation of the model can be done based on experimental cases, as we did in the framework of the GEMMA project.

Generation IV Materials Maturity (GEMMA)

The research leading to these results has been carried out in the frame of EERA Joint Programme on Nuclear Materials and is partly funded by the European Commission HORIZON 2020 Framework Programme under grant agreement No. 755269

Thermo-mechanical-metallurgical couplings

The treatment of welds and weld residual stresses in the R6 defect assessment procedure

Mike Smith – University of Manchester

GEMMA workshop, 4th-5th October 2021

Talk content

- Introduction – The UK regulatory environment
- What is R6 used for?
- What does R6 contain?
- Weld-specific advice in R6
- Estimation of as-welded residual stresses
 - Simplified advice
 - Finite element simulation and validation
- Impact of PWHT, prior loading, and elevated temperatures
- Handling of welds and residual stress in an R6 assessment

UK Civil Nuclear Regulatory Environment

- The Office of Nuclear Regulation license and regulate nuclear operators
 - Regulation is non-prescriptive
 - ONR define Nuclear Safety Principles
 - The licensee must demonstrate how they meet those principles
- This places a considerable technical responsibility on the licensee

Structural integrity assessment requirements depend on the safety significance of the plant – on the frequency and tolerability of failure

Tolerable Failure Frequency	Defect tolerance assessment required?
Frequent ($>10^{-3}$ pa)	None
Infrequent ($10^{-3} > f > 10^{-5}$ pa)	Only if known defects or active cracking mechanism
High Integrity ($10^{-5} > f > 10^{-7}$ pa)	Yes
Incredibility of failure ($< 10^{-7}$ pa)	Yes

Relatively large numbers of components and welds require assessment, both as part of the basic plant safety case, and to sentence defects found during in-service inspections

Assessments and ISI concentrate on welds, so residual stresses are potentially very important

R6: Assessment of the integrity of structures containing defects

- *Or: “It operates outside the creep regime, and it may contain a crack-like defect – how fast / how much will it grow? How big can it get before it fails? Will it go Bang or Squish?”*
- First issued in 1976, now at Revision 4 Amendment 12
- Maintained by EDF Energy, EASL, Jacobs, Rolls Royce, TWI, Fraser-Nash, National Nuclear Laboratory, and NRG.
- Influenced other Codes and Standards worldwide (BS7910, API579, SINTAP, SKIFS:1994 ...)
- Based on the Failure Assessment Diagram (FAD)
- Basic and alternative approaches (*quick, cheap and conservative versus slow, expensive and accurate*)

Assessment of the Integrity of Structures Containing Defects

R6 is divided into five chapters:

I - Basic Procedure

includes load and stress categorization, constructing the FAD, type of analysis (initiation or tearing), Evaluation of K_r and L_r , assessment of significance, and reporting

II - Inputs to Basic Procedures

II.1: Tensile Properties

II.2: Fracture Toughness Values

II.3: Characterisation of Flaw

II.4: Plastic Limit Load Analysis

II.5: Stress Intensity Factor Solutions

II.6: Treatment of Combined Primary and Secondary Stresses

II.7: Treatment of Welding Residual Stresses

II.8: Evaluation of Fatigue and Environmentally Assisted Crack Growth

R6 is divided into five chapters:

III - Alternative Approaches (more sophisticated analyses)

III.1: Guidance on Selection of Alternative Approaches

III.2: Guidance on Finite-Element Methods

III.3: J-Estimation Approaches

III.4: Sustained Loading

III.5: Evaluation Under Mode I, II and III Loads

III.6: Assessment of the Integrity of Structures Made of C-Mn (Mild) Steels

III.7: Allowance for Constraint Effects

III.8: Allowance for Strength Mis-Match Effects

III.9: Guidance on Local Approach Methods

III.10: Load History Effects

III.11: A Procedure for Leak-Before-Break Assessment

III.12: Assessment Using Crack Arrest

III.13: Probabilistic Fracture Mechanics Procedure

III.14: Treatment of Displacement-Controlled Loading

III.15: Calculation of Residual Stress in Weldments

III.16: Assessment of Strain-Controlled Loadings

R6 is divided into five chapters:

IV - Compendia

IV.1: Limit Load Solutions for Homogeneous Components

IV.2: Limit Load solutions for Strength Mis-Match

IV.3: Stress Intensity Factor Solutions

IV.4: Welding Residual Stress Distributions

IV.5: Compendium of β Solutions

V - Validation and Worked Examples

V.1: Validation of Basic Procedures

V.2: Validation of Alternative Approaches

V.3: Worked Examples of Basic Procedures

V.4: Worked Examples of Alternative Approaches

V.5: Validation Sheets for the Calculation of Residual Stress in Weldments

V.6: Worked Example of the Calculation of Residual Stress in Weldments

Weld-specific advice in R6, other than residual stresses

II.1: Tensile Properties

Needed to calculate reference stress and L_r

Advice on evaluating relevant weld data (large scale longitudinal and cross-weld, local DIC and micro-tensile)

II.2: Fracture Toughness Values

Needed to calculate K_r

Advice on testing weld metal (retained RS, mis-match, relevance of material chosen for testing, location of crack growth plane)

II.3: Characterisation of Flaw

Advice on NDE procedures for welds

II.4: Plastic Limit Load Analysis; III.8: Allowance for Strength Mis-Match Effects; IV.2: Limit Load solutions for Strength Mis-Match.

Advice on calculating reference stress & L_r in over-matched and under-matched welds

Estimating the magnitude and distribution of as-welded residual stresses – R6 Section II.7

- R6 defines as-welded WRS profiles at level 1, level 2, and level 3
 - Level 1 - yield membrane
 - Level 2 - upper bound compendium profiles from Section IV.4
 - Level 3 – combined FE simulation and measurement from Section III.15
- Level 1 and level 2 profiles are often very conservative
 - Upper bounds based on the literature creep inexorably towards yield
- Level 3 profiles require considerable effort to generate
 - Their use can have a dramatic effect on the assessment

The impact of post-weld processing on residual stresses

- Post-weld heat treatment
 - Simple approaches: relevant proof stress at PWHT temperature, or “custom and practice” for specific applications
 - Analytical methods – use $R5 V 2/3$ to calculate stress relaxation
 - Finite element simulation
- “Proof testing” or load history effects
 - Simple advice
- Operation at high temperatures
 - Simple advice (yield strength at temperature, effect of modulus change)
- Cast in the form of review / advice rather than Prescription

R6 Section III.15 – Finite element prediction of residual stresses in weldments

- Based upon UK nuclear industry experience of residual stress modeling and measurement from 1995 to 2008
- Compiled by a steering group (Rolls-Royce, EDF, AMEC, Manchester University, the Open University and Frazer-Nash Consultancy), and peer reviewed by Battelle (USA) and AREVA (Germany)
- Originally published in R6 in 2009
- Cover the prediction and validation of residual stresses in austenitic steel similar metal welds made with arc-welding processes
- Aimed at prediction of stresses, not distortion
- Do not explicitly cover PWHT or dissimilar metal welds but have been applied to both
- Under development to extend to ferritic welds with phase transformation

Content of R6 Section III.15

- Define analysis objectives
- Collect input data
 - (especially covering materials data and material models)
- Consider resources available
- Decide weld modeling approach
- Create Finite Element model
- Perform thermal analysis
 - (with detailed advice on weld heat source models)
- Perform mechanical analysis
- **Validate analysis**
- Perform sensitivity studies

Validation requirements for Level 3 residual stresses

- R6 does not allow finite element predictions of residual stress to be used in integrity assessments without appropriate validation against measured stresses.
- The level of validation depends on the application
 - Stress corrosion or cleavage fracture may require high standards of validation
 - Fatigue crack growth or ductile fracture may require less
- Validation may be achieved through:
 - RS measurements on a dedicated weld mock-up (**high**). Diverse methods (eg diffraction and strain relief) recommended
 - Capability demonstration against relevant benchmark mock-ups (**medium**)
– **R6 Section V**
 - Comparison with published measured data for a representative weldment (**low**)
- R6 also requires sensitivity studies to demonstrate that the simulation results are robust

R6 Section V.5 – validation sheets for the calculation of residual stress in weldments

- Well-characterised benchmark problems to validate finite element WRS predictions
 - Problem definitions
 - Measured thermal solution validation data (metallography & thermocouples)
 - Measured residual stresses
 - FE performance measures
- Three benchmarks and one worked example currently in R6 – all have performance criteria, based on temperatures, stresses, SIF
 - NeT TG1 single bead on plate
 - Austenitic edge-welded beam
 - NeT TG4 3-pass slot weld
 - One and three pass austenitic groove weld (worked example)
- A number under development
 - Multi-pass pipe girth welds
 - NeT TG5 ferritic edge-welded beam
 - EB welds in ferritic and austenitic steels

Using residual stress in the assessment 1 - The R6 FAD

- R6 is a two-parameter assessment method
- The cracked structure is assessed against its proximity to both fracture (via K_r) and plastic collapse (via L_r)
- R6 uses a failure assessment diagram (FAD), which accounts for the interaction between the two mechanisms
- The FAD is formally defined as:
- $FAD = \sqrt{J_e/J}$

Using residual stress in the assessment 2 – basic definitions

- K_I^p = Linear elastic stress intensity factor due to applied *primary* loads (those that can cause collapse).
- K_I^s = Linear elastic stress intensity factor due to applied *secondary* loads (those that do not contribute to collapse).
- K_{mat} = Material fracture resistance
- V = Plasticity correction factor for the interaction between primary and secondary loads

$$K_r = (K_I^p + VK_I^s) / K_{mat}$$

$$L_r = \frac{\textit{Total applied primary load}}{\textit{Plastic yield load of cracked structure}}$$

- Or, alternatively the ***reference stress*** is $L_r\sigma_y$
- **A weld residual stress is normally treated as a secondary load – R6 requires the elastic stress intensity factor due to the RS field**

Alternatively, R6 is a J-estimation procedure

- The failure assessment line is equivalent to $f(L_r) = \sqrt{J_e/J}$
- For purely primary loading $K_J = \frac{K_I^p}{f(L_r)}$

- Residual stresses are treated as secondary loads

$$K_J = \frac{K_I^p + VK_I^s}{f(L_r)}$$

- The V-factor has to account for both **increases** in J caused by plastic interaction between primary and secondary loads ($V>1$), **decreases** caused by mechanical relaxation of secondary stresses at high L_r ($V<1$), and **limits** caused by plastic relief of excessive secondary stresses (like PTS – $V<1$)
- R6 Section II.6 gives several routes to calculate V, with increasing sophistication and decreasing conservatism
- The correct values of V for weld residual stress are a subject for debate

R6 assessment of secondary stresses: the NeSC-1 spinning cylinder large-scale PTS test

- NeSC-1 “modelled” a pressurized large LOCA
- R6 was compared with cracked body FE predictions of J for a large surface breaking defect (defect “R”)
- The conservatism inherent in different R6 approaches are evident

Summary

- R6 gives a wide range of advice for defect assessments in welds, covering most of their characteristic features
- However, there is still active development underway, particularly:
 - Better “level 2” RS profiles
 - Predicting RS and microstructure in transforming steels
 - Quantifying and reducing conservatism in combined loading assessments
 - Quantitative handling of the effects of PWHT